

**STUDY FOR MODELING AND SIMULATION OF CONVECTIVE
PROCESSES IN ATMOSPHERE**

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STATEMENT BY CANDIDATE

As required by the University Ordinances 770 and 771, I wish to state that the work embodied in this thesis entitled “**Study for modeling and simulation of convective processes in atmosphere**” forms my own contribution to the research work carried out under the guidance of **Dr. Pradip Sarawade** and **Dr. Bhupesh Adhikary** at the Department of Physics, University of Mumbai, Vidyanagari, Santacruz – E, Mumbai – 400098, India and International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development, Kathmandu, Nepal.

This work has not been submitted for any other degree of this or any other university. Whenever references have been made to previous work of others, it has been clearly indicated as such and included in the Bibliography.

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Statement required under the ordinance 771 regarding the new fact

This thesis describes the presence of persistent and significant amount of Black Carbon (BC) aerosols at mid-troposphere: at and above 500 hPa in the atmosphere over South Asia. This thesis used the Weather Research Forecasting model coupled with Chemistry (WRF-Chem) and various satellite, reanalysis, and in-situ observation products to support the findings. This research shows the effect of Black carbon by direct and indirect means over South Asia using the case study of extreme events. First time reported feature of BC by this study was far away from the major sources of emissions. This thesis shows the potential of BC in absorbing solar radiation and altering weather parameters near the surface which reduces the dispersion condition. BC's potential in cloud property is also examined in this study. This also evaluated the performance and the limitation of WRF-Chem model for complex terrain at different resolutions.

The new facts that have emerged from this work are as follows:

- ✓ Presence of persistent BC plume at 500 hPa and above over central India during summer monsoon season.
- ✓ On a daily scale, BC uplift during strong Convective Available Potential Energy/Helicity period can transport a significant amount of BC from the surface to around 850 hPa, but not up to the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere.
- ✓ Advection of BC from IGP to central Himalaya mountain cities needs better parameterization for improvement in model performance over these cities/regions.
- ✓ Aerosol increases/decreases precipitation by 10-100 mm/day during extreme precipitation event.
- ✓ At cloud-resolving resolution, aerosols don't vary precipitation significantly.
- ✓ BC strongly affects incoming/ outgoing radiation flux and its effect on regional weather is evident immediately.

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The work reported in this thesis has been done under the guidance of Dr. Pradip Sarawade and co-guidance of Dr. Bhupesh Adhikary. The experimental work has been carried out by me and the results have been jointly interpreted by us. The results of part of this work have already been published in reputed international journals, some are under communication.

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This is to certify that **Mr. Singh Prashant Ram Urmila** has duly completed his thesis for the degree of Ph.D. of the University of Mumbai and his thesis entitled “**Study for modeling and simulation of convective processes in atmosphere**” is up to the standards both in respect to its content and literacy presentation for being referred to an examiner.

We further certify that the entire work has been done by the candidate under our guidance and that no part of it has been submitted previously for any degree or diploma of any university.

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Abstract

The Indian subcontinent or specifically South Asian countries are known as the hotspot of anthropogenic emissions along with some other Asian countries. Economy and lifestyle in South Asia completely depend on the monsoon precipitation in this region. In the current decade, South Asia is facing frequent flood and drought over many parts of India and neighbouring countries. This study tried to analyse the motion of pollutants specifically black carbon (BC) during the active convective period of monsoon over South Asia and its interaction with weather and climate parameters using the Weather Research Forecasting model coupled with Chemistry (WRF-Chem). BC is known as the second-largest radiative forcing agent; it affects radiative forcing and contributes to climate change. The thesis work identified the first time the presence of consistent and significant BC layer at mid-troposphere during monsoon over South Asia using WRF-Chem simulation for the year 2013. The presence of an anti-cyclonic region during the monsoon season at the higher troposphere (500-300 hPa) contributes to this stable BC layer. The mid-troposphere is a place where most of the cloud forms, this layer can potentially affect cloud formation and monsoon over India by the direct and indirect effect. Further, this work identifies the BC transports mechanism from the source of emission to the free troposphere and upper troposphere during the active convective period. Although individual high convection days (high helicity/CAPE) can easily transport a significant amount of BC from the surface to the FT, simulations do not show significant BC transported to the upper troposphere-lower stratosphere during these days. While satellite-derived products provide some insights into model predictions, there is a need for in-situ measurements of BC concentration aloft over South Asia to further constrain model performance and improve understanding of BC transport to FT.

Real-time open biomass burning (OBB) events analysed to understand the effect of BC on radiative forcing. Seasonal open biomass burning contributes to significant carbonaceous aerosol, especially BC loading over South Asia. Analysis of emissions during active fire seasons reveals that Punjab emissions increase by approximately 83-106% compared to anthropogenic emissions, while Myanmar emissions increase by 2338-3054% based on Fire Inventory (FINN) model results. Results from a year-long simulation are examined during the post-monsoon and pre-monsoon periods when active fires are reported. Results show that carbonaceous aerosol from open biomass burning is lofted up to 3-5 km vertically; horizontally, these aerosols rise to 850 hPa from the surface and disperse throughout South Asia. Radiative forcing calculations suggest changes up to -6.14 W/m^2 at the surface, while -0.50 W/m^2 at top of the atmosphere over Punjab, and similarly -42.76 W/m^2 at the surface and -1.91 W/m^2 at top of the atmosphere over Myanmar. Further, results show that surface temperature decreased by 2K, relative humidity changed by 8%, and the planetary boundary layer changed up to 600m. Changes in precipitation patterns and volume due to carbonaceous aerosol from open biomass burning were not evident.

To understand the effect of aerosols (specially BC) on cloud and precipitation we analysed Kedarnath flood case. Fast-moving monsoon, pre-existing westerlies, and orographic uplifting were reported in previous research as the major reason for cloud burst over Kedarnath. We did multiple simulations using WRF-Chem different mechanisms at different resolutions, all simulations captured spatial and temporal patterns of observed precipitation and another thermodynamical variable. The result shows up to 20-50% changes in the rain over the area near Kedarnath due to aerosols. Significant changes in cloud property, rain concentration, and ice concentration within the cloud are simulated in the presence of aerosols. Due to aerosol–radiation feedback, the important indices in severe weather prediction shows significant positive changes near Kedarnath. Aerosols play a

crucial role in the monsoon-cloud-precipitation mechanism, detailed profiling and study of such aerosols are important over the Indian subcontinent.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

In recent decades, South Asia is one of the fastest developing regions on the world map in terms of population and industries. It is a group of eight countries namely, Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka. Amongst these, India is the largest country in terms of area, population, and economy. The economy of all these South Asian countries are dependent on monsoon precipitation, which is an uncertain phenomenon. Many planetary and seasonal scale circulations such as El-Nino Southern Oscillation (ENSO), Madden–Julian oscillation (MJO), Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD), etc. complicates the prediction of monsoon circulation phenomenon. Further, changing aerosols concentration and heating of the northern Indian region, plays a very important role in monsoon flow and precipitation. Monsoon precipitation further gets complex due to complicated Aerosol-Cloud-Precipitation processes in the atmosphere. In this chapter, I will briefly go through the Indian Summer Monsoon, also known as South Asian Summer Monsoon, convection process over South Asian region and black carbon's potential effect on weather and climate systems. Finally, I will also explain the regional model and satellite data used for this work and objective of the thesis.

1.1. Summer Monsoon

Since ancient times, the summer monsoon is an important synoptic-scale phenomenon for entire Asia, especially the southern part (Indian subcontinent). As monsoon is the main source of water and this part of the world is still developing; hence the agriculture is dominantly dependent on monsoon [1,2]. The Indian summer monsoon is a result of the dynamic interaction between the land, ocean and atmosphere. Monsoon is driven by ocean-land heat gradient and tropospheric latent heating. Heating over Indian subcontinent creates a

low-pressure zone over the northern Indian subcontinent and high-pressure zone over the ocean due to its relatively low temperature, leading to monsoon circulation from ocean to land [2].

The monsoon in Indian subcontinent is an intercontinental climate circulation system. It impacts about 60% of the world's population [3, 4]. Also, the effect of El Nino and La Nina, generally referred to as El Nino and Southern Oscillation (ENSO) are very pronounced on the South Asian monsoon cycle. They affect moisture intake and results in either a deficient or surplus monsoon precipitation [5–11]. Another phenomena known as Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) are also associated with enhancement or suppression of atmospheric convection over the western part of the equatorial Indian Ocean and vice versa for eastern part [8].

The three months (March, April, and May) before the South Asian monsoon onset, is generally referred to as the pre-monsoon season. During this period, over the Indian subcontinent, the days are hot with convective and mesoscale circulation contributing to 12-14% of total rain [12]. Surface winds swing from weak easterly to westerly and anti-cyclonic region forms in northern India which enhances convective activity [13,14]. The transition from pre-monsoon to monsoon is led by surface heating which further enhances convection activity and cloud coverage [15].

The onset of South Asian Monsoon (SAM) over the Indian subcontinent is observed with changes in the circulation pattern in the lower atmosphere. This is driven by intense heat low regions generated in northern Indian subcontinent and strong southwest winds reaching the southern cost of India. This process leads to rainfall greater than 5mm for a period of more than 5 days over Kerala [16,17], indicating the presence of SAM. Duration of SAM is approximately 4 months and this period is traditionally observed from June to September,

further categorized into active and break phases. These break phases appear just before the withdrawal of monsoon [18]. Withdrawal of summer monsoon begins when low-level westerlies weaken over the Arabian Sea, Indian landmass and Bay of Bengal, while the upper level easterly gets built up [19].

Fig. 1.1: Normal monsoon propagation has taken from Bookhagen et al. (2005).

1.2. Convection

Convection is simply uplifting of mass due to temperature gradient in the system and is a key process to re-distribute the temperature and momentum in atmospheric columns. Atmospheric convection is referred to as uplifting of warmer air parcel towards the higher and cooler section of atmosphere, this is due to atmospheric instability produced by the temperature gradient in the planetary boundary layer (PBL). Generally, atmospheric convection leads to severe weather like thunderstorms, hail, downbursts, and tornados; more than 57% worldwide catastrophic deaths are associated with them [20].

Fig. 1.2: Schematic presentation of atmospheric convection, reproduced from <http://apollo.lsc.vsc.edu/>.

The life cycle and size of convection makes the weather phenomenon associated with them difficult to forecast. It is an integrated process between the atmosphere, land, moisture and heat due to radiation from the sun. Further, rainfall associated with convection over the Indian subcontinent varies on the temporal and spatial scale depending on season, topography and orography of the region. Also, the nature of convection varies from season to season; during pre-monsoon convection it is mostly localized whereas during monsoon it is synoptic.

For deep convection event, environment needs to be in an unstable state, to provide necessary bounce to the atmospheric moisture parcel. For synoptic-scale convection, few additional conditions need to be satisfied such as low-level convergence, rising motion and wind shear.

For modeling, the convection parameterization is one of the complicated mechanisms, requiring different parameterization schemes for shallow or deep convection. Also, modeling the convection is dependent on choices of resolution and different parameterization schemes

related to radiation, planetary boundary layer. Model simulation at the horizontal resolution of 4 km or finer provides a better convection parameterization over different topographic regions and conditions [21].

1.3. Black Carbon

Black carbon (BC) is a product of the combustion process, a large fraction of BC comes from anthropogenic emissions. Therefore, most of the BC emissions come from transport, industries, residential and open fire. BC plays an important role in climate and weather studies as it interacts with solar radiation, cloud process, snow and ice cover.

Fig. 1.3: Black carbon sources and processes that control in atmosphere, reproduced from Bond et al., (2013) [22].

BC is distinct from other carbon compound aerosols and poses certain unique properties, such as strong visible light absorption of at least $5 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$ at 550 nm, refractory with vaporization temperature near 4000K, aggregate morphology and insolubility in water and common organic solvents. BC is the result of incomplete combustion of carbon-rich fuel in absence of oxygen, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon molecules form precursors of BC. Below electron microscopy images show wrinkled graphite layers forming a shell around a hollow or disordered interior. Transmission electron microscope image of chain-like BC and aggregate BC are also shown; the size of BC is in few nanometres. The density of BC is estimated in between 0.625 to 2.25 g/cm^3 based on source and condition of emission in various studies.

Fig. 1.4: *Black carbon aggregates a) Scanning electron microscope images , b and c) transmission electron microscope images, reproduced from Bond et al., (2013) [22].*

Climate forcing of BC is estimated as $+1.1 \text{ W/m}^2$, which is the second-largest forcing agent after CO_2 ($+1.56 \text{ W/m}^2$). Different studies range BC climate forcing from $+0.17$ to $+2.1 \text{ W/m}^2$. BC direct climate forcing is considered in terms of atmospheric absorption and scattering [22, 23]. Whereas indirect or semi-direct effect of it can be accounted via liquid cloud effect, mixed-phase cloud, ice cloud and snow-ice effect.

Various studies estimate that the emission rate of BC over India ranges from 400-1300 Gg/yr. The lifetime of BC is assumed ~ 7 days varying from 3 to 11 days in various studies. BC plays a crucial role in weather and climate system; it absorbs visible light and

warms the atmosphere. BC also scatters visible light that reduces the top of atmosphere (TOA) radiation.

BC strongly affects the cloud properties such as cloud cover, emissivity, and brightness. Atmospheric heating due to BC can lead to different distribution of clouds. It may change the cloud condensation number and ice number concentration within the cloud that affects the lifetime of the cloud. It affects the precipitation pattern and phase partitioning in mixed-phase clouds. Deposited BC on glaciers reduces albedo by absorption of visible light and changes the size and morphology of ice and snow. BC indirect/semi-direct forcing due to interaction with snow and cloud is evident in many studies that contribute to total climate forcing. Since BC is emitted in the lower atmosphere it shows many health effects like adverse respiratory and cardiovascular problems.

1.4. Weather Research and Forecasting model

Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model is a mesoscale weather prediction model used for prediction and research purposes worldwide. It is developed and maintained by National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) group, along with the contributions from many researchers round the world [24].

Fig. 1.5: Weather Research Forecasting flow chart has taken from NCAR website (https://www2.mmm.ucar.edu/wrf/users/docs/user_guide_V3.9/ARWUsersGuideV3.9.pdf).

In this thesis, we used Advanced Research WRF (ARW) version 3.8 for all the simulations. WRF modeling system consists of WRF pre-processing System (WPS), ARW solver and a post-processing and visualization tool. WPS creates a background for simulation such as simulation domain, map projection, interpolate terrain and geographical data, interpolate meteorological and sea surface data. ARW solver is the heart of the modeling system and it is composed of many initialization programs necessary for the simulation. WRF has fully compressible non-hydrostatic equations available along with hydrostatic options too. It allows the regional and global application, two- or single-way horizontal nesting, vertical nesting, and many more options.

Multiphysics options for land-surface, planetary boundary layer, atmospheric and surface radiation, microphysics and cumulus convection are also included in it. WRF uses Arakawa C-grid staggering for grid system, Runge-Kutta 2nd and 3rd order time integration options, scalar-conserving flux form for prognostic variables and 2nd to 6th order advection options for horizontal and vertical grids. Fluid dynamics options are available as monotonic

transport and positive-definite advection option for moisture, scalar, tracer and turbulence kinetic energy (TKE). Upper boundary absorption and Rayleigh damping are used in WRF. Once ARW solver simulates the real or idealized condition various post-processing tools are available to visualize and analyse the output of the simulation. In this thesis, we have intensively used NCAR Command Language (NCL) for analysis and visualization.

Fig. 1.6: WRF model coupled with Chemistry flow chart has taken from NCAR website (https://www2.mmm.ucar.edu/wrf/users/docs/user_guide_V3.9/ARWUsersGuideV3.9.pdf).

We have used the WRF model coupled with the chemistry option (WRF-Chem) [25] for simulation in this study. WRF-Chem is the same as WRF model with several additional chemistry calculation packages coupled with WRF simulation. For chemistry option, several

additional gridded input data like biogenic emission, fire emission, and GOCART background needs to feed during real.exe; anthropogenic emission and boundary condition during WRF solver. For making chemical input separate codes must be used, as per the choice of chemistry model is used in simulation.

Chem package consists of a dry deposition scheme coupled with soil and vegetation schemes. WRF-Chem can be simulated with anthropogenic emission, such as EDGAR anthropogenic emission or user-provided emissions. Chem package also provides several choices of gas-phase chemical mechanisms, aerosol mechanism and photolysis mechanism. The aerosol direct and indirect effect through the interaction of photolysis, atmospheric radiation and microphysics are available in the current version of the model. Several additional features are available in WRF-Chem package to work with volcanic ash, wildfire and different size of aerosols.

The major difference between WRF and WRF-Chem is that WRF-Chem requires many additional inputs describing the origin of chemical species and additional calculation. Those inputs can be prepared in the required format for model simulation using various tools. Some of the model or codes creates all the required input in single run whereas few requires several steps to create all the inputs. In this research study, we had used NCAR utility tool to create all the required input emission data for simulations as per the required domain and chemical mechanism. Following paragraphs discuss the different type of emissions and utility tools used in this study to make input for the simulation. Repository of all data emission and utility tool is available at UCAR website (<https://www.acom.ucar.edu/wrf-chem/download.shtml>).

Anthropogenic emissions are known as emissions associated with human activity. In this thesis, we used the Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR) with

Hemispheric Transport of Air Pollution (HTAP) for creating anthropogenic emission input. EDGAR-HTAP is gridded air pollution emission dataset based on national inventories, it is available at $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ horizontal resolution. EDGAR-HTAP emission inventory consists many species like CH₄, NMVOC, CO, SO₂, NO_x, NH₃, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, BC and OC prepared with base year 2010 [26]. FORTRAN based pre-processing tools (anthro_emiss) are available from the above link to convert global inventory to project on our domain. This tool helps to resize the resolution of anthropogenic emission from standard resolution to domain-specific resolution [27]. Several options are available in the pre-processing tool related to how many frames we need to generate in the input file.

Model of Emissions of Gases and Aerosols from Nature (MEGAN) is used to estimate the net emission of gases and aerosols from terrestrial ecosystems into the atmosphere. This data is derived from landcover, atmospheric chemistry and local regional weather, it is available at as high as 1 km horizontal resolution. Both FORTRAN utility code (bio_emiss) and required input data can be obtained from the above link of UCAR. Monthly biogenic flux from MEGAN is available as an offline model or we can incorporate it as the on-line mode to couple land surface biogenic emission to WRF-Chem [28, 29].

Open biomass burning including forest fire is one of the major sources of emission in atmosphere. In this research study, we used Fire INventory from NCAR (FINN), Version 1 as fire emission inputs. Required pre-processing FORTRAN codes and data is available at UCAR website (<http://bai.acom.ucar.edu/Data/fire/>). FINN is available at the 1 km horizontal resolution on daily basis. Utility tool (fire_emis) provides a flexibility to select emission species and time frequency of input data to project on required domain of simulation. Both smouldering and flaming emissions are included in the mapped data set. In addition, open west burning data is available at $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ resolution [30, 31].

O₂ and O₃ column densities are provided as input in simulation. The utility tool `exo_coldens` available at UCAR website is used to project on required domain. This input is required for photolysis processes in MOZART/MOZCART option in WRF-Chem simulation. Further initial and boundary condition is used from the Model for Ozone and related chemical Tracers, version 4 (Mozart-4) [32]. FORTRAN utility code (`mozbc`) is available on UCAR website and simulation output of offline MOZART4 simulation is available at <https://www.acom.ucar.edu/wrf-chem/mozart.shtml>.

1.5. Reanalysis and Satellite data

The thesis research uses various satellite products and in-situ data, then re-analysis products for validation of model and discussion of findings. The following section describes the satellites, re-analysis and in-situ data with some uncertainty.

Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Applications (MERRA) is a NASA product based on Goddard Earth Observing System model (GEOS-5) atmospheric data assimilation system. MERRA is available at $0.5^\circ \times 0.66^\circ$ horizontal layer with 72 vertical layers from surface to 0.01 hPa. MERRA uses various satellite products to complete a set of assimilated data product [33]. Many observational bias corrections are incorporated into MERRA real time product during assimilation. We used aerosol and meteorological products from MERRA at various stages of research in this thesis. Detailed information is available at MERRA working article. Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) reanalysis data is also used in understanding the trend of meteorological and chemical variables over the region of study. Four dimensional variational (4D-VAR) is further used to assimilate model and satellite data in CAMS. Meteorological parameters and chemical species at different

pressure level, time steps and different resolution are available within CAMS reanalysis and near real time database [34].

This study used Tropical Rainfall Measurement Mission (TRMM) data to understand the convection trend using lightning and precipitation data over South Asia. The lightning dataset is available at $1.25^\circ \times 1.25^\circ$ spatial and daily temporal resolution. TRMM uses space-based lightning imaging sensor to detect total lightning product which accounts for flashes derived from cloud-to-cloud, intra-cloud and cloud-to-ground lightning. The combined lightning flash rate from Optical Transient Detector (OTD) and Lightning Imaging Sensor (LIS) instruments are accessible from mid-1995 to early 2015 [35–37]. TRMM monthly level 3 data (TRMM_3A12) available at resolution $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ is used to analyse the general trend over the region of study. Further analysis is performed using TRMM-TMPA (Multi-satellite Precipitation) level 3 data at $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ spatial resolution available 3 hourly.

Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) at 0.55 micron for land and ocean data from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), onboard the TERRA and AQUA satellites was used to evaluate model generated AOD. We used level 3 monthly dataset (MOD08_M3 and MYD08_M3 combined dark target and deep blue algorithm) at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ spatial resolution available from the website [38–40]. MOD08 relation with AERONET observation is discussed in detail in research article [41]. MODIS level 3 Terra (MOD08_D3) and Aqua (MYD08_D3) daily product available at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ resolution were also used along with AIRS. Both the satellite products provide cloud fraction, cloud top pressure and temperature, which are useful to understand the cloud properties.

The Cloud-Aerosol LIDAR and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observation (CALIPSO) uses active LIDAR and passive infrared (IR) sensors to measure vertical profile of the atmosphere, including cloud and aerosol types [42, 43]. CALIPSO image products are used to

understand the observed vertical aerosol lifting based on the available satellite overpass during the entire season and for event specific case studies. CALIPSO level 3 gridded data (CAL_LID_L3_APro_Combined-Beta-V1) obtained from CALIPSO data site is used to understand the 2D feature of smoke plumes over South Asia. This product is available at the resolution $2^{\circ} \times 5^{\circ}$ [44,45]. CALIPSO images were used to understand fire emissions from the available satellite overpass during the active biomass burning events in this study. Specifically, CALIPSO level 1 version 3.3 data with air pollution speciation (clean marine, dust, polluted continental, clean continental, polluted dust and smoke) was used in this study.

Multi-angle Imaging Spectro-Radiometer (MISR) gridded level 3 monthly product at $0.5^{\circ} \times 0.5^{\circ}$ resolution (MISR_AM1_CGAS_0_5_DEG_FIRSTLOOK) obtained from above link used to evaluate seasonal AOD and absorbing aerosol optical depth (AAOD) [46, 47].

Atmospheric infrared sounder (AIRS) Aqua level 3 daily product available at $1^{\circ} \times 1^{\circ}$ resolution (AIRX3STD) was used to understand the cloud property during heavy precipitation event. Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) gridded data at the resolution of $1^{\circ} \times 1^{\circ}$ (OMI-Aura_L3-OMAERUVd) was used to understand seasonal AAOD over South Asia [48]. OMI absorbing aerosol can be systematically affected by local sources at that scale without affecting regional AAOD, more details are available in OMI-ATBD (Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document) and user guide [49].

AOD data is also used from the AERONET (Aerosol RObotic NETwork) within the model domain for 2013. AERONET is National Aeronautics and Space Administration's (NASA) ground-based remote sensing aerosol measurement network. AERONET level-2 monthly averaged data was considered in this study for comparison with model data. AERONET level-2 data is automatically cloud cleared and the instrument was calibrated

before the field installation. AERONET uses CIMEL's CE318 sensor which is a multiband sun photometer that measures solar irradiation [50].

1.6. Objective of this research study

The present research study is oriented towards simulation of WRF-chem and other chemical transport model to study BC vertical lifting with atmospheric convection and its impact on convective precipitation over regional level. Further investigation was applied to understand the role of BC in convective instability and precipitation processes over South Asia. Specific goals of the thesis are:

1. Simulation using Weather Research and Forecasting model coupled with Chemistry (WRF-Chem) to understand the convection over South Asia.
2. Understand the vertical transport of BC in atmosphere during convection.
3. Analyse the role of BC in precipitation and cloud interaction over South Asia.
4. Understand the effect of BC on weather and convective transport of air parcel in atmosphere.
5. Compare modelling results with satellite and re-analysis data to validate results.

1.7. Thesis overview

This thesis discusses in detail the uplifting of black carbon in the free troposphere during the convective period over South Asia and its possible effect on radiative forcing and cloud formation. This thesis is first to report the presence of a significant layer of BC at and above 500 hPa in the atmosphere over the central part of India during the monsoon period. The thesis covers the main objective as mentioned in section 1.6 through the following chapters.

Chapter 1 basically covers the current knowledge from the literature on Indian summer monsoon, convection process in the atmosphere, black carbon in the atmosphere and its direct-indirect interaction with the atmosphere. A detailed description of the WRF model with chemistry along with various reanalysis and satellite observational data used in this research is provided.

Chapter 2 covers the process of BC transport during monsoon synoptic convection and individual convection events. The observed modeling and satellite observation features of BC in a free atmosphere and vertical transport is discussed in detail.

Chapter 3 uses various simulations to understand the role of carbonaceous aerosols on the radiative forcing of atmosphere and its immediate effect on regional and local weather.

Chapter 4 uses various model simulations, along with satellite and in-situ data to understand the role of BC and aerosols on cloud microphysics and precipitation during extreme precipitation cases.

Chapter 5 provides a brief summary of the research performed in this thesis and provides the future importance of the reported work.

Chapter 2: Transport of black carbon from planetary boundary layer to free troposphere during the summer monsoon over South Asia¹

2.1 Background

BC contributed to global temperature rise by $\sim 1^\circ\text{C}$ and changes up to $\sim 1\text{mm}$ rainfall have been reported in the literature [51]. Several studies have reported positive feedback of aerosols on precipitation; more aerosols leads to less precipitation which feedbacks to more aerosol concentration over the Indian monsoon region [52–55]. Absorbing aerosols (like BC) heat the surrounding atmospheric layer, which leads to atmospheric instability and vertical motion over the region [54,56,57]. Changes in convection activity over the eastern coast of India, due to alteration of stability produced by aerosols has been previously reported[58].

Observations over different cities in South Asia show distinct seasonal cycle of BC surface concentration; highest in winter, reduced in pre-monsoon and lower during the monsoon season [59–64]. Cloud-Aerosol Interaction and Precipitation Enhancement Experiment (CAIPEEX) carried out during 30th August, 4th and 6th September, 2009 (monsoon period) over Brahmaputra river valley of India, measured significant amount 1500 ng/m^3 of BC in the vertical 1-3 km of atmosphere and 300 ng/m^3 of BC up to 6 km [65,66]. Balloon-based experiment over Hyderabad (17.38°N , 78.48°E) on 17th March 2010 (pre monsoon) measured two elevated peaks of BC concentration at 4.5 km and 8.3 km. The

¹ This Chapter is adapted from “Transport of black carbon from planetary boundary layer to free troposphere during the summer monsoon over South Asia” P. Singh, P. Sarawade, B. Adhikary, Atmospheric Research (2019) (IF=4.11).

concentration was more than $12 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively [67]. However, this study was limited in duration of observation and limited in modeling approach, therefore sources of elevated BC was not confirmed fully. Observation using unmanned aerial vehicle over the Indian Ocean during March, 2006 reports BC concentration from $0.07 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to $0.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at 1500 a.m.s.l. [68].

Chemical transport model based BC characterization over South Asia are limited [27,62,69,70]. These model-based studies have shed light into seasonal cycle, vertical distribution and source apportionment of BC over South Asia. Some other model studies have focused on the aerosol interaction between upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS) over Asia [71–73] and over other part of world [69,74].

Recently conducted AEROCOM (Aerosol Comparison between Observations and Models) modeling analysis using WRF-Chem simulation for 5 years (2010-2014) [75] and multi model study for 2 years (2008-2009) [76] presented global BC concentration. Eckhardt et al., (2015) concluded that performance of chemical transport model does not depends on the class of model used for the simulation [76]. AEROCOM II used 13 aerosol model and 4 aircraft measurement to compare BC vertical concentration, reported BC radiative forcing $+0.23 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$ globally whereas A-FORCE experiment show $+0.98 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$ over Japan [77–80]. Bond et al., (2013) reports $+1.1 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$ total climate radiative forcing produced by BC [22].

This chapter provides a brief discussion about BC lofting to higher altitude using the WRF-Chem model. Possible factors affecting the BC seasonal trend of Himalayan cities (such as Kathmandu), the problem reported in previous studies [27,70] is discussed in this paper. Vertical transport of BC from source of emission to FT is discussed in detail on seasonal scale over South Asia. This study discusses in detail the convection transport of BC in free troposphere during pre-monsoon and monsoon season over South Asia. The paper also

discusses elevated BC layer over South Asia during anticyclonic SAM period at various pressure level.

2.2 Data and Methodology

2.2.1. Observations

This study uses Tropical Rainfall Measurement Mission (TRMM) data to understand convection trends in South Asia. This dataset is available at the $1.25^\circ \times 1.25^\circ$ spatial and daily temporal resolution. TRMM uses space-based lightning imaging sensors to detect the total lightning product which accounts for flashes derived from cloud-to-cloud, intra-cloud and cloud-to-ground lightning (https://lightning.nsstc.nasa.gov/lis/overview_lis_instrument.html). The combined lightning flash rate from the Optical Transient Detector (OTD) and Lightning Imaging Sensor (LIS) instruments are available from mid-1995 to early 2015 [35–37].

The Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) at 0.55 micron for land and ocean data from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) onboard the TERRA and AQUA satellites was used to evaluate the model generated AOD. We use the level 3 monthly dataset (MOD08_M3 and MYD08_M3 combined dark target and deep blue algorithm) at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ spatial resolution available from the website (<https://search.earthdata.nasa.gov/>). Product details are available in research papers [38–40]. The MOD08 relation with AERONET observation is discussed in detail by Ruiz-Arias et al. (2013) [41].

The Multi-angle Imaging Spectro-Radiometer (MISR) gridded level 3 monthly product at $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ resolution (MISR_AM1_CGAS_0_5_DEG_FIRSTLOOK) obtained from the above link was used to evaluate the seasonal AOD and the absorbing aerosol optical depth (AAOD) [46,47]. A single scattering albedo (SSA) and AOD is used to calculate a

particular wavelength AOD in MISR [81]. Uncertainties related to the AOD calculation fully depends on how good the AOD and SSA are captured by MISR.

We use the Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) gridded data at resolution of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ (OMI-Aura_L3-OMAERUVd) obtained from (https://disc.gsfc.nasa.gov/datasets/OMAERUVd_003/summary) to understand seasonal AOD over South Asia. OMI absorbing aerosol can be systematically affected by local sources at that scale without affecting the regional AOD (for more details, see OMI-ATBD [Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document] and user guide) [49].

The Cloud-Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observation (CALIPSO) (<https://www-calipso.larc.nasa.gov/about/payload.php#CALIOP>) uses active lidar and passive infrared (IR) sensors to measure the vertical profile of the atmosphere including cloud and aerosol types [42,43]. We use CALIPSO image products from (https://www-calipso.larc.nasa.gov/products/lidar/browse_images/production/), based on the available satellite overpass, to understand the observed vertical aerosol lifting during the entire season and for event specific case studies. CALIPSO level 3 gridded data (CAL_LID_L3_APro_Combined-Beta-V1) obtained from (<https://search.earthdata.nasa.gov/>) is used to understand the 2D feature of smoke plumes over South Asia. This product is available at the resolution $2^\circ \times 5^\circ$ [44,45]. Extinction coefficient from CALIPSO level 2 data (CAL_LID_L2_05kmAPro-Standard-V4) is used to understand aerosol profile over the region of interest.

We also use AOD data from the AERONET (AERosol RObotic NETwork) within the model domain for 2013. AERONET is National Aeronautics and Space Administration's (NASA) ground-based remote sensing aerosol measurement network (<https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/>). For purposes of comparison with satellite and model AOD,

we took into consideration AERONET level-2 monthly averaged data in this study. AERONET level-2 data is automatically cloud cleared and the instrument is calibrated before field installation. AERONET uses the CIMEL's CE318 sensor which is a multiband sun photometer that measures sun irradiation [50].

2.2.2. Chemical Transport Model

The Weather Research Forecasting model [82] coupled with the chemistry option (WRF-Chem,) version 3.8.1 is used in this study to understand vertical transport and distribution of BC over South Asia [25]. The model geographic domain is defined on Mercator projection centred at 22°N, 78°E with 203 grids east to west and 130 grids north to south. This translates into an area covering 6.5°-36.0°N, 53.0°-103.0°E at a spatial resolution of 25x25 km, (Fig. 2.1). The model consists of 40 vertical levels; the vertical height of the first 10 levels is within 300 m while the levels above are within 650 m of each other.

The Emission Database for Global Atmospheric Research-Hemispheric Transport of Air Pollution (EDGAR-HTAP) offers anthropogenic emission of CH₄, OC, SO₂, NO_x, NMVOC, NH₃, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, BC and OC (http://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/htap_v2/index.php?SECURE=123). EDGAR-HTAP annual emissions are available at the 0.1°×0.1° spatial resolution for 2010 [83]. We used the 2010 emissions and mapped them onto our model domain using the EDGAR-HTAP preprocessor tool available from the NCAR website [27].

Since open biomass burning of agricultural crop residue and forests contributes significantly to BC loading over South Asia [84,85], the study uses emission estimate from the Fire INventory from the NCAR model version1 (FINNv1) which provides daily open-burning-based emission estimates at the 1 km × 1 km spatial resolution (<https://www2.acom.ucar.edu/modeling/finn-fire-inventory-ncar>) [31]. The fire toolkit

available from the NCAR website is used to map the FINNv1 emission to the WRF-Chem modeling framework.

The modeling framework uses the time-varying boundary and initial chemical condition generated from the Model for Ozone and Related chemical Tracers, version 4 (Mozart-4) (<https://www.acom.ucar.edu/wrf-chem/mozart.shtml>). The MOZBC utility is used to initiate WRF-Chem simulations. MOZART-4 is the offline global chemical transport model which includes 85 trace gases, 12 bulk aerosols with 39 photolysis, and 157 gas-phase reactions [32].

The O₂ and O₃ column densities are generated by the `exo_coldens` utility tool, available from the NCAR website, which is used in the base photolysis subroutines of the WRF-Chem MOZART/MOZCART option. The monthly biogenic flux is introduced in WRF-Chem simulation using the Model of Emissions of Gases and Aerosols from Nature version 2.1 (MEGAN2.1). MEGAN is available as an offline model to couple the land surface biogenic emission to WRF-Chem [29].

The WRF-Chem simulation uses the Thompson scheme [86] for bulk microphysical parameterization and adopts the convective parameterization following the Kain–Fritsch Scheme [87]. The planetary boundary layer (PBL) physics option selected is the Yonsei University Scheme (YSU) which uses the revised vertical diffusion package with a nonlocal turbulent mixing coefficient in the PBL [88]. Shortwave and longwave radiation physics were used as suggested in the Dudhia Shortwave Scheme [89] and RRTM Longwave Scheme [90], respectively. We used the Unified Noah Land Surface Model scheme for the land-atmosphere interaction in the model [91] and the MM5 Similarity Scheme in the surface layer option [92]. The daily sea surface temperature (SST) was updated in the model simulation using data available from (<http://polar.ncep.noaa.gov/mrab/translation.shtml>).

The air pollutant simulation for this study uses MOZCART chemistry, which combines the MOZART model-based trace gas chemistry with the Goddard Chemistry Aerosol Radiation and Transport (GOCART) model based on the bulk aerosols chemistry options. The photolysis option is selected as the Madronich fast-Ultraviolet-Visible Model (F-TUV) [93] as suggested in the WRF-Chem manual which will be used with the MOZCART based chemistry option. Dust emission is selected as in GOCART chemistry and provided with a fractional erosion map. Dimethyl sulfide (DMS) emissions are kept active as the GOCART scheme which uses DMS emission from the sea surface [94]. The MOZCART based biomass burning emission and plume rise calculation is used for FINNv1 data as mentioned above.

2.2.3. Methodology

We use TRMM based lightning flash rate data to understand convection climatology in the coastal city of Mumbai (19.07° N, 72.87° E) in the Western Ghats (WG), the IGP city of Lucknow (26.84° N, 80.94° E), the city of Kolkata (22.57° N, 88.36° E) situated in an area influenced by the Bay of Bengal (BoB), and Kathmandu (27.71° N, 85.32° E), a mountainous city located in the Himalayas. The selection of cities (read as points) in this study has been based on the diverse orographic conditions and influence of monsoon activity. Mumbai, a coastal city in India, has a very dense population and is situated west of the Western Ghats (WG); Lucknow falls within the Indo-Gangetic plain (IGP), India, and is considered as the hotspot of pollution in South Asia [95]; Kathmandu is a high elevation mountain valley city in Nepal; and Kolkata is situated north of the Bay of Bengal (BoB) and is strongly affected by BoB wind flow. We also perform pollutant trend analysis over mountainous or foothills cities such as Dehradun (30.31° N, 78.03° E), Shimla (31.10° N, 77.17° E), Nainital (29.38° N, 79.46° E), Dharamshala (32.21° N, 76.32° E), Thimpu (27.47° N, 89.63° E), Shillong (25.57° N, 91.89° E), Dibrugarh (27.47° N, 94.91° E) and Itanagar (27.71° N, 93.62° E) in

this study to understand lofting over complex terrain. Again, these locations are representative of the area and do not necessarily represent the actual urban city as the model grid is too coarse to capture just urban emission details. Based on the climatology data for Oceanic Niño Index (ONI) available from (http://origin.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/products/analysis_monitoring/ensostuff/ONI_v5.php) and TRMM lightning data, we carried out an yearlong WRF-Chem simulation for the South Asian domain for 2013. We chose 2013 as that year was classified as a climatologically normal year with no influence of La Nina or El Nino observed. However, the year experienced one of the longest monsoon seasons as per the monsoon arrival and departure reports of the Meteorological Department (IMD) of India and the Department of Hydrology and Meteorology (DHM) of Nepal. Using the traditional classification of seasons over South Asia as well as the observations of monsoon activity by IMD and DHM, we have arrived at a classification of four different seasons for the purposes of this study; winter (December 2012 - February 2013), summer or pre-monsoon (March – 9th June), monsoon (10th June – 15th October) and post-monsoon (16th October – 30 November, 2013).

2.3. Results and Discussion

2.3.1. Convection Climatology

Thunder and lightning are considered as a signature of deep convection events [37]. The availability of lightning detection data from space-borne instruments between 1995 and 2015 allows for climate scale analysis of the phenomena over South Asia. Fig. 2.1 shows the sea surface temperature (SST) anomaly (a solid black curve) which is an indication of ENSO strength [96] and the lightning flash rate count for selected cities (read areas) indicating the strength of convection over the region. The SST anomaly data (right axis) shows several El

Nino and La Nina events with differing intensities [97]. While the results show that the year 1997 recorded very strong El Nino with 2.4°C , the year 2000 recorded strong La Nina with -1.7°C . We did not however observe any apparent trends in the data; nor was there any strong periodicity. In more recent times, 2010 seems to have been a strong La Nina with -1.6°C while 2011 has been a moderate La Nina with -1.4°C . In contrast, 2013 seems to have been neither a strong El Nino year nor a strong La Nina year.

Fig. 2.1 also shows the lightning flash rate count for the four cities. The solid dark green and dark pink curves illustrate the results for Kolkata and Mumbai, which fall immediately in the monsoon flow from the BoB and Arabian Sea (AS). The dashed red and blue lines show results for Lucknow and Kathmandu, respectively, which are further inland.

The results show that Kolkata faces the maximum flashes, followed by Lucknow, which is situated in the IGP area. This is barring some cases of moderate El Nino (2001-02) and moderate La Nina (2010-11) events where Lucknow reports a higher flash rate. Using TRMM data, Cecil et al. (2014) found that the maximum flash rate over South Asia of $18/\text{km}^2/\text{month}$ was reported in the Brahmaputra River Valley (BRV). The valley is about 350 km away from Kolkata. While most of the cities, which were part of our research, show a singular peak lightning flash rate per year during the pre-monsoon and early monsoon seasons, Mumbai shows dual peaks per year coinciding with the onset and reversal of the monsoons. The results further indicate that the Mumbai dual peaks are more pronounced during the La Nina years, barring 2003-04 and 2009-10 which were, respectively, weak and strong El Nino years. The Mumbai results also show that, generally, flash rate peak values are greater during the reversal of the monsoon than at the onset. However, Mumbai faces least number of flashes compared to the other three cities. The values for Lucknow are higher than those for Kathmandu with some exceptions being observed during the strong La Nina (1996-

97)/El Nino (2009-10) years. The strong El Nino years show lower flash rates than average for all cities whereas the La Nina years record more lightning in general.

Since lightning is a proxy for convective weather, based on this climatological analysis, it is expected that pollutants would be lofted higher over Kolkata and the IGP region than Mumbai and Kathmandu if all other factors remain the same. But Mumbai would see significant pollutants lofted during both the onset and reversal of the monsoons while the other three regions would see significant lofting only during the pre-monsoon season. During the post-monsoon and winter seasons, it is expected that vertical transport would be greatly reduced due to very weak convective activity. This paper reports the vertical transport of black carbon aerosol during 2012-2013 as previously mentioned.

Fig. 2.1. Time series of the lightning flash rate over Mumbai (solid dark pink), Kolkata (solid dark green), Lucknow (dashed red) and Kathmandu (dashed blue) with Sea Surface Temperature (SST) anomaly (solid black).

2.3.2. Model Performance Evaluation

Fig. 2.2 shows the annual and seasonal average surface concentrations generated from the WRF-Chem model. The results (Fig. 2.2a) show that, on an annual basis, IGP has a significantly high concentration of BC along with some of the major cities on the western and eastern coast of India. Agricultural burning during the pre-monsoon season and high BC emissions from densely urbanized/industrialized areas during other seasons has led to IGP being dubbed the pollutant hotspot in South Asia. Since seasonal elevation/spike in pollutant levels has been previously reported and analysed [98–101], it is not the focus of our analysis.

Simulation results show a significant increase in surface BC concentration over Myanmar during the pre-monsoon season due to open forest fires (Fig. 2.2b) as reported above. In addition, our simulation captures elevated concentrations over many Indian cities like Delhi, Mumbai, Surat, Vadodara, Kolkata and Chennai. Cities on the eastern coast of India, especially the area around Kolkata, also show higher BC concentrations with some reduction during the monsoon period (Fig. 2.2c). While the southern Indian states do not show much difference between the annual and pre-monsoon BC concentration, they show a significant reduction during the monsoon season. The modeled results show that both the Bay of Bengal and the Arabian Sea have reduced BC loading during the monsoon season compared to their annual and pre-monsoon averages.

Kumar et al. (2015) had used the WRF-Chem model to show surface BC concentration over India at a horizontal resolution of $10 \text{ km} \times 10 \text{ km}$ [27]. Their simulation captured the major features and seasonality of BC concentration for all the regions of South Asia except for that over the Himalayan region. Adhikary et al. (2007) showed surface BC over the South Asian domain at a coarser resolution of $50 \text{ km} \times 50 \text{ km}$ [70], which also captured major features such as the elevated rates of BC concentration in the IGP and Myanmar regions. But both these studies were not able to capture the seasonality of BC

concentration in Himalayan cities such as Kathmandu. The current study uses a spatial resolution of $25 \text{ km} \times 25 \text{ km}$ which falls between the resolutions used by Kumar et al. (2015) and Adhikary et al. (2007), all of them able to capture the regional scale spatial features within the modeling domain. Eckhardt et al. (2015) has, moreover, reported that the model horizontal resolution alone does not significantly alter spatial features for primary aerosols such as BC [76].

Fig. 2.2. BC concentration over the modeling domain: (a) annual average and seasonal averages for (b) pre-monsoon period and (c) monsoon period.

The modelled surface average BC concentration over South Asia is in the range of many in-situ observations reported in the literature (Fig. 2.3). The model is also able to capture the seasonal trend in many places although the model is not able to reproduce the high daily average concentrations over Himalayan cities like Kathmandu [102] and Srinagar [103] for the entire year. Similarly, winter (Fig. 2.3a) and post-monsoon (Fig. 2.3b) BC concentration is not simulated well over foothill cities like Dibrugarh [104] and Guwahati [105]. However, observed BC concentration over cities like Dhanbad [106], Kolkata [61], Hyderabad [107] and Anantpur [108] are simulated well in the model.

Fig. 2.3. Seasonal comparison of BC concentration at different sites with model (a) Winter, (b) Pre-Monsoon, (c) Monsoon and (d) Post-Monsoon.

Since this study focuses on understanding BC transport to the free troposphere (FT) during the active convection period, we discuss model performance with columnar aerosol optical depth from satellites and ground-based monitoring network. Since the climatology

results presented in Fig. 2.1 show that pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons are convective periods, we evaluate model AOD with observations to assess columnar pollutant loading over the region during this time.

Fig. 2.4. Average AOD over the domain for pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons obtained from MISR (a & b), MODIS (c & d) and model (e & f).

AOD is the extinction of solar radiation due to the presence of aerosol particles in the atmospheric column. Higher AOD implies that there is a higher concentration of particulates atmospheric columns and vice versa. Fig. 2.4 shows averaged pre-monsoon and monsoon AOD from MISR and MODIS (Terra and Aqua) satellites and the WRF-Chem model. MISR (Fig. a-b) retrieval illustrates many finer scale features with elevated AOD over the IGP-Kolkata region. MISR results also show elevated AOD over Myanmar as well as outflow over the Western Ghats during the pre-monsoon period along with elevated AOD over the western boundary during both seasons. MODIS results (Fig. 2.4c) show elevated AOD over the IGP and Kolkata regions and Western Ghats outflow during the pre-monsoon season. MODIS level 3 products also have large data gap areas. MODIS results also show elevated AOD over Northern India and the Arabian Sea during the monsoon season (Fig. 2.4d). CALIPSO derived AOD shows basic feature over Indian region, due to horizontal distribution of AOD is affected by limited data coverage (Fig 2.4.1). CALIPSO retrievals show high AOD over northern and central India, during pre-monsoon while the region is significantly cleaner during the monsoon. CALIPSO shows elevated AOD over Arabian Sea during pre-monsoon and monsoon periods but relatively cleaner Bay of Bengal during the monsoon. Since CALIPSO level 3 product is at very coarse resolution $2^{\circ}\times 5^{\circ}$ [44] it is able to capture coarse features only.

Fig. 2.4.1: *CALIPSO aerosol optical depth during Pre- monsoon and Monsoon over the domain.*

Results of MODIS and MISR both show elevated AOD over the Bay of Bengal during both the pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons. Fig. 2.4 e-f shows the modeled AOD results. During the pre-monsoon season, although the model over-predicts the AOD over Myanmar and Eastern India, it captures the elevated AOD over the IGP and Kolkata regions. The model also simulates the pollutant outflow from the Western Ghats during the pre-monsoon season. Elevated AOD over the western boundary over Oman and the Arabian Sea is also well captured by the model. The model however shows a strong north-south gradient over the Bay of Bengal and the Arabian Sea which is not that prominent in satellite products. The features of the major hotspot are captured well in the model simulation with respect to satellite observation and in-situ data as also documented in the study on India [109].

Table 2.1 shows the available AOD from the AERONET sites in South Asia along with satellite AOD (MISR, MODIS Terra and Aqua) for pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons. AERONET AOD data were available for nine South Asian sites for 2013, four in India, one in Bangladesh, two in Nepal and two in Pakistan. The model simulated AOD values are within the range for most of the sites during both the monsoon and pre-monsoon seasons when evaluated against AERONET or satellite observations. But the model shows substantial over-prediction over Pokhara, a mountainous city in Nepal, during the pre-monsoon season while the values falls within the range of satellite and AERONET observations during the monsoon season. The aerosol transport over mountain areas is discussed further in Section 2.3.3. The model also shows substantial under-prediction over Lahore, a megacity in South Asia, the local emissions of which may not have been captured by the current emissions inventory. MODIS shows better agreement with modeled AOD over IGP whereas MISR

agrees well with modeled AOD over oceans and coastal areas as well as the Myanmar area. Previous studies have reported that MODIS performance is better over land where dense vegetation is present while MISR performs well near oceans [110,111].

Table 2.1. Average AOD from satellites, AERONET observation and model simulation for monsoon and pre-monsoon seasons over different cities of South Asia.

Location	Elevation	Monsoon				Pre-Monsoon			
		MISR	MODIS	AERONET	Model	MISR	MODIS	AERONET	Model
Pokhara (28.15N, 83.97E)	807	0.35	0.22	0.22	0.41	0.21	0.38	0.71	0.42
Dhaka(23.73N,90.40E)	34	0.71	0.50	0.51	0.54	NA	0.77	0.79	0.84
Gandhi College (25.87N,84.19E)	60	0.52	0.72	0.72	0.65	0.44	0.55	0.62	0.64
Kanpur (26.51N,80.23E)	123	0.46	0.89	0.63	0.67	0.55	0.50	0.55	0.57
Jaipur (26.91N,75.81E)	450	0.40	0.51	0.49	0.56	0.36	0.22	0.39	0.49
Karachi(24.87N,67.03E)	49	0.42	0.56	N/A	0.44	0.60	0.45	0.28	0.45
Lahore(31.54N,74.33E)	270	0.51	1.15	0.89	0.73	0.73	0.52	0.53	0.57
Lumbini(27.49N,83.28E)	110	0.64	0.64	0.51	0.59	0.47	0.66	0.67	0.60
Pune(18.54N,73.81E)	559	0.42	N/A	0.35	0.40	NA	0.33	0.33	0.43

Fig. 2.5 shows absorbing aerosol optical depth (AAOD) from MISR (a & c) and OMI (b & d) during the pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons, respectively. MISR AAOD (Fig 2.5a and 2.5c) shows elevated AAOD over the Bay of Bengal and the Arabian Sea compared to the rest of the model domain. While OMI AAOD shows elevated AOD over the Tibetan Plateau and most of the continental areas except India during the pre-monsoon season, AAOD is present throughout the domain during the monsoon period. Components of MISR absorbing optical depth include BC, organic carbon and brown carbon where the MISR retrieval uncertainties belong to a choice of surface and aerosols [112]. The OMI absorbing aerosol optical depth can be considered as a signature of absorbing aerosol such as BC but, sometimes, freshly emitted soot results in over-estimation of AAOD [113]. These AAOD will help to constrain modeled BC distribution during the two seasons.

Fig. 2.5. Absorbing aerosol optical depth from MISR (a,c) and OMI (b,d) during pre-monsoon and monsoon respectively.

2.3.3. Seasonal and vertical distribution

Given our model's ability to simulate BC over South Asia, we discuss BC distribution during different seasons in different layers of the atmosphere. Fig. 2.6 presents the pre-monsoon and monsoon average BC concentrations at 850 hPa, 500 hPa and 300 hPa. These layers are generally used to evaluate the top of the boundary layer, the mid troposphere level and the near tropopause layer [114]. While Fig. 2.2 shows IGP and other major cities with elevated BC concentrations on an annual scale, that same pattern is not apparent in Fig. 2.6 indicating the effect of the emissions and convective transport.

Fig. 2.6. Seasonal average BC concentration from model during pre-monsoon (a,e,i) and monsoon (c,g,k) at different pressure levels (850hPa, 500hPa, 300hPa), respectively. CALIPSO smoke detection frequency during pre-monsoon (b,f,j) and monsoon (d,h,l) at different heights (below 2km, 4.5-6.5 km, and above 9km from mean sea level), respectively.

Fig. 2.6a shows that, during the pre-monsoon season, horizontal BC distribution at the 850 hPa is like the surface layer indicating strong vertical transport over the region. The 850 hPa results show elevated BC concentration over north-eastern India, Bangladesh and the Myanmar region like the surface concentration shown in Fig. 2.2. Both Fig. 2.2 and 2.6a show elevated concentration over the middle east with plumes reaching out to the Arabian Sea. At the higher level, i.e., 500 hPa, the north-eastern plume is still present while an elevated pollution plume can be seen in the north-western region. At even higher levels, the strong jet stream disperses the plumes resulting in elevated concentration seen over the eastern Himalayas. In addition, a strong north-south gradient of the pollutants is also evident at this layer. The seminal paper by Lau and Kim (2006) has reported on the uplift of BC and dust over the Indian subcontinent with implications for the monsoon [115]. They reported

that while rainfall increased from 20°-28°N, it decreased over the central part (10°-20°N) due to dust and BC loading in the months of May and June. However, the authors do not provide specific concentration amounts in their paper.

During the monsoon, as in the pre-monsoon season, the 850 hPa layer shows similar BC concentration features like surface concentration. But there is substantial reduction in the BC concentration along the north-south gradient. Thus, the southern edge of the modeling domain shows very clean conditions not seen during other seasons. On the other hand, the IGP region still shows elevated average BC concentrations of around $1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ despite wet removal via monsoon rains. At 500 hPa, the winds are generally weaker over much of South Asia compared to the winter and pre-monsoon seasons (Fig. 2.6.1). The low winds over the central and eastern parts of India and winds from the weakened westerlies (in a north to southwestern direction) and monsoon winds from BoB (in a south-western to north-eastern direction) provide conditions for pollutant accumulation at this layer over central India. This feature, as shown in Fig. 2.6g, is isolated and homogenous in concentration throughout much of central India. A similar pattern is observed at 300 hPa. However, the shape of the plume is stretched in an east-west direction. At 300 hPa, the model shows easterly winds over southern India while it is westerly over TP and the weak winds over IGP and central India contribute to the stretching of the plume in an east-west direction. It is difficult to ascertain this persistent BC plume over central India as observations are not readily available. But model simulations can be evaluated with AOD and AAOD observations to some extent as discussed previously. Although these columnar satellite products do not constrain the vertical layers, they do show elevated AAOD and AOD over much of the area depicted in the model simulations. We therefore evaluate a coarser satellite derived product in next section for constraining this modeled result for vertical layers.

Fig. 2.6.1: Average Wind at 850 hPa, 500 hPa and 300 hPa during winter, Pre-Monsoon and Monsoon.

The CALIPSO level 3 product (CAL_LID_L3_APro_Combined-Beta-V1- see papers [44,45] shows the increased frequency of a smoke layer below 2 km over Myanmar and south eastern India during the pre-monsoon season. Uncertainties in CALIPSO observations are related to detection and wrong attribution of the types of aerosols in different sky conditions. This study also analysed the smoke + polluted continental aerosol detection frequency (Fig. 2.6.2) but the results look like the smoke frequency. The polluted dust shows increased detection over dust source regions. During the monsoon, the level 3 product (Fig. 2.6d) shows a substantially higher frequency of smoke detected over IGP and central India. At upper layers, especially between 4.5–6.5 km, detection frequency increases over central and eastern India as well as IGP during the pre-monsoon season while the monsoon shows

elevated smoke detection over much of India and the Bay of Bengal. Even higher up, i.e., above 9km, the detection frequency is significantly higher over central India compared to the Tibetan Plateau as previously reported in other studies [44,116] and consistent with our current model simulation. But, while aerosol aloft during the pre-monsoon season has been analysed at great length, our study shows that aerosols should also be examined further during the monsoon period for its impact on monsoonal precipitation. Future studies should examine if this is an anomaly for 2013 or if the feature is present for other years as well. Studies by Fortems-Cheiney et al. (2011) and Girach and Nair (2014) using MOPITT, CO also show elevated concentrations over East Asia extending all the way to the Indian sub-continent. Our model simulation for the year 2013 also shows a similar CO plume (Fig. 2.6.3) as described in the Lelieveld et al. (2018) study undertaken during 2015 [119] but different from the BC plume as discussed in Fig. 2.6k. However, though CO and BC are different species with differing emissions and transport processes, they often co-relate well with each other [120–122].

Fig. 2.6.2: CALIPSO smoke + polluted dust detection frequency during pre-monsoon and monsoon at different heights.

In WRF-Chem model, we can differentiate between hydrophilic and hydrophobic BC. Our simulations show a similar plume feature with just hydrophobic BC indicating that the feature is from fresh BC emissions in the region and not from elsewhere. Further, this result implies that the observed BC concentration plume at 500-300 hPa is from active convection

and monsoon circulation within South Asia. We performed a one-month long simulation for July 2013, the active monsoon phase, without boundary conditions from the global models to verify the role of global transport in high elevation BC concentration. The results suggest that the areas near the boundaries are cleaner compared to simulations with updated boundaries from the global model. The feature over the mainland at 850 hPa, 500 hPa and 300 hPa is still present in the simulation with minor differences. This outcome implies that the elevated BC at 500 hPa and 300 hPa is mostly from regional pollution with a small fraction from global transportation.

Fig. 2.6.3: CO concentration at above 250 hPa from WRF-Chem simulation for 2013 and as reported in Lelieveld et al., (2018) for 2015.

To our knowledge, this elevated concentration of the BC plume in the 500-300 hPa over central India has not been noticed previously. Much of the published previous literature discusses pollutants in the UTLS region over South Asia, with implications for hemispherical transport and stratospheric concentrations [115,119,123]. Samset et al. (2013) discuss the location of BC plumes in the vertical however; the vertical distribution with respect to the latitudinal gradient over India remains poorly characterized for its impact on the monsoon. It is well known that BC influences the monsoon directly through radiative forcing and indirectly through cloud micro physics. The question remains whether this feature is present

in other years or is only specific to the year we simulated. The CALIPSO level 3 product for 2014 shows a similar monsoon feature with some differences in detection frequency and shape. Questions remain, however, regarding the sensitivity of observed concentration as different models could simulate differing concentrations due to differences in their transport and removal processes. Ultimately the question remains whether this concentration can significantly impact monsoon circulation to alter rainfall in the region. During the pre-monsoon (March-April-May) season, a temperature change of $-0.15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 850 hPa and 0.81 mm/day decrease in precipitation over central and northern India have been reported by Meehl et al. (2008). However, the study only reports BC AOD, not concentration. Menon et al. (2002) also reported a 0.5 mm/day decrease in precipitation in the region and, as with Meehl et al. (2008), reports only BC AOD strength, not concentration [123,124]. Although Lelieveld et al. (2018) reports 200-300 pptv of Organic Carbon (OC) between 200 and 100 hPa when discussing air pollution vertical transport [119], the study does not provide estimates of BC concentration in the vertical layers. Our model predicted OC is in the same range as that reported by Lelieveld et al. (2018).

Previous studies over the Asian domain suggests the presence of pollutants above 200 hPa during the summer monsoon season (June-August) dominated by anti-cyclonic activity [73,119]. This feature is also replicated in our model. But the previous studies put the feature more towards north than our model simulation, which is further supported by CALIPSO smoke and polluted continental aerosol type detection over the same region.

Fig. 2.8 gives the model-simulated BC time series data over Mumbai, Lucknow, Kathmandu, and Kolkata. Mumbai and Kolkata show similar trends, i.e., significantly higher BC concentration during winters, which illustrates mega city emission coupled with lower PBL height during winter. On the other hand, the IGP city of Lucknow shows similar

concentrations throughout the year, pointing to the regional dominance of air pollutants over local sources. The city of Kathmandu, on the other hand, shows a higher concentration during the pre-monsoon season, possibly due to the influence of open biomass burning, than during the winter season. The results show the influence of the summer monsoon lowering the near surface concentration in all the cities although this influence is not as strong over Lucknow. All four cities show traces of BC reaching around 11km during the monsoon season. The majority of BC concentration is within 1.5 km for all the cities discussed with occasional higher transport. Hence, during the monsoon season, due to the convective uplifting of BC and then advection by synoptic winds, the free troposphere over South Asia is more polluted than during other times of the year.

Model simulations over Kathmandu and Srinagar, both mountainous cities, show different trends from the observations. Observations point to higher concentrations during the winter compared to the pre-monsoon season (Fig. 2.3). Kumar et al. (2015) have reported similar problems for other mountain cities such as Dehradun [27]. They attribute this model error to local emissions which are not captured by the emissions inventory used in their study. Mues et al. (2017) also used the WRF-Chem model to simulate BC over Kathmandu during the winter and pre-monsoon seasons [125]. The study reported that the model underestimated the observed concentration and that a month-long simulation representing both winter and pre-monsoon seasons did not show any significant difference in concentration. Mues et al. (2017) also attributed this model limitation to lack of a proper emissions inventory. In our study, we analysed the problem in relation to different mountainous cities, namely, Dharamshala, Nainital, Dehradun, Shimla, Kathmandu, Thimpu, Shillong and Itanagar. In all these cities, the model simulation shows higher near-surface BC concentration during the pre-monsoon season compared to the winter season. We examined the hydrophobic and hydrophilic BC for these cities to understand local versus long range transported BC. In the

model, conversion from hydrophobic to hydrophilic BC is based on a fixed conversion time of 2.5 days. This allows some room for interpretation between local and regional transport of BC. Our analysis of the cities does not show any significant seasonality of hydrophobic BC while hydrophilic BC shows elevated concentration during the pre-monsoon season. Thus, some elevated pre-monsoon concentration in the model can be attributed to spring open burning which is prevalent in the region. Some of the model limitations maybe also overcome by examining the parameterization used to allocate anthropogenic emission seasonality in these models. Since any observed concentration is affected by both emissions and prevailing meteorology, we examined the latitudinal cross-section over these cities to assess the pollutant transport from IGP during the pre-monsoon season. Our results reveal significant pollutant transport from IGP in the western and central Himalayan cities compared to the eastern Himalayan cities proportional to anthropogenic emissions strength. Our study recommends examining, in a future study, how the contribution of IGP BC emissions coupled with variations of PBL height lead to increased concentration over these mountain cities.

In order to understand the seasonality of BC concentration over South Asia, a yearlong simulation without convective wet scavenging was undertaken. The results show that near surface concentration in this simulation is much higher during the monsoon season than during the rest of the year. South Asia sees significant convective activity during the pre-monsoon season as shown in Fig. 2.1. The ability of the model to capture this phenomenon has implications for near surface BC concentration in the source region. In trying to capture overall seasonality (i.e., observed higher concentration in winter than in the pre-monsoon), it could further lower the concentration during the pre-monsoon season in the mountain cities. However, this then leads to severe under-estimation of BC concentration over south Asia by our model as well as all the other global and regional models previously discussed.

Fig. 2.7. CALIPSO extinction coefficient profile over central India during July month

To further understand vertical uplift and advection of aerosols over the region, we examined CALIPSO passes over the Indian subcontinent during 2013 (the CALIPSO data and analysis used are discussed in the observations section). Our analysis reveals (Fig. 2.7.1) aerosol plumes generally below 3 km during the 2012-2013 winter season. During the pre-monsoon season, CALIPSO derived aerosol profiles show pollutant plumes reaching up to approximately 5 km (Fig. 2.7.2). During the monsoon season, the results show pollution sometimes reaching up to 9–11 km which is evident with extinction coefficient profiles (selected profiles from July) from CALIPSO over central India (Fig. 2.7) and smoke plume shows similar results (2.7.3). All profiles for the July month are presented in the supplementary material (Fig. 2.7.4) that shows peak of extinction coefficient between 5 to 10 km over central India. Monthly average extinction coefficient from CALIPSO shows good agreement with the WRF-Chem extinction coefficient (Fig. 2.7.5). These results are broadly

consistent with model-based findings. However, since CALIPSO derived data do not reveal concentration amounts, the comparison is highly qualitative.

Fig. 2.7.1: Wintertime CALIPOS pass from central India, upper panel shows WRF-Chem points BC concentration at respective points shown in CALIPOS image. Lower panel shows night-time passes.

Fig. 2.7.2: Pre-monsoon time CALIPOS pass from central India, upper panel shows WRF-Chem points BC concentration at respective points shown in CALIPOS image. Lower panel shows night-time passes.

Fig. 2.7.3: Monsoon time CALIPOS pass from central India, upper panel shows WRF-Chem points BC concentration at respective points shown in CALIPOS image. Lower panel shows night-time passes.

Fig. 2.7.4: CALIPSO derived extinction coefficient over central India for all passes during July 2013.

Fig. 2.7.5: CALIPSO and WRF-Chem extinction coefficient over central India for July 2013.

Fig. 2.8. Annual atmospheric profile concentration of BC (above ground level) for the selected cities of (a) Mumbai, (b) Lucknow, (c) Kathmandu, and (d) Kolkata.

2.3.4. Case studies of vertical transport

This section presents results from specific event days when BC could be potentially lifted very high into the troposphere. The two cases we examined are based on updraft due to helicity (UH) and convective available potential energy (CAPE). High helicity and CAPE values represent an unstable atmosphere conducive for active convection. UH is the strength of cyclonic updraft rotation in the atmosphere, calculated from the surface to 3 km in the model [126]. Larger the value of helicity, stronger is the potential for vertical transport. UH is calculated using the ‘helicity’ function available from WRF. CAPE provides the strength of air parcel updraft due to buoyancy, calculated between the level of free convection (LFC) and level of environmental equilibrium (EL) or level of neutral buoyancy [87,127,128]. CAPE is

calculated using function ‘cape_2d’ available from the WRF users’ website. High CAPE values indicate a very unstable atmospheric condition and strong vertical motion.

Table 2.2. *Dates of Helicity and CAPE based cases with values.*

City (lat.,long.)	Helicity Cases(0-3Km) (m-2/s-2)				CAPE Cases (J/Kg)			
	Low		High		Low		High	
	Date	Helicity	Date	Helicity	Date	CAPE	Date	CAPE
Mumbai(19.08°N, 72.88°E)	20/03	-2.96	14/03	319.60	27/04	13	23/04	2242
Kolkata(22.57°N, 88.36°E)	24/03	-47.53	31/03	344	16/05	261	03/05	4754
Kathmandu(27.72°N, 85.32°E)	07/03	-3.31	10/03	264.88	10/04	0	17/04	837
Lucknow(26.85°N, 80.95°E)	16/04	-0.75	14/03	518	06/04	0	18/04	1688

We identified days where CAPE values were maximum and minimum for all four selected cities throughout the pre-monsoon season. Similarly, we chose days where there was maximum helicity and compared it with days when the helicity was at its minimum during the pre-monsoon season. We specifically chose high and low event days within a week or two of each other such that monthly and seasonal biases did not influence our comparison significantly. Table 2.2 shows the modeled UH and CAPE values for the selected days.

The tabular data shows that minimum helicity values are lower than zero for all the cities for the days considered while the maximum values range from 260-518 m²/s² indicating the difference in helicity strength considered for BC uplift. Similarly, minimum CAPE values are below 300 J/Kg while maximum value ranges from 800-4800 J/Kg. UH values lower than 150 m²/s² and CAPE values lower than 500J/kg indicating a very stable atmosphere [129,130]. Kunz (2007) and Tajbakhsh et al. (2012) have reported that CAPE values > ~1400 J/kg represent severe weather for the continental USA [130,131]. We are not aware of any such threshold values for South Asia. Our model-based calculation therefore

seems to point to low to moderate helicity cases considered for BC uplift while moderate to very high CAPE values for convective BC uplift.

Fig. 2.9 and 2.10 show vertical BC concentration over the four cities (regions) during low/high UH and CAPE values for the days presented in Table 2.2. Since both UH and CAPE phenomena are synoptic scale features, we show a wider geographical space rather than confine them to a singular grid value. The centre of the horizontal axis of each subfigure is of the exact latitude and longitude of the city in consideration. Figures in panel (a) show a fixed longitude with varying latitudes while panel (b) figures show fixed latitude with varying longitudes for the low UH and CAPE cases. Similarly, panel (c) and (d) in both Fig. 2.9 and 2.10 are for high UH and CAPE values.

As shown in Fig. 2.9, Kolkata, Kathmandu and Lucknow show substantial differences in BC vertical distribution between low UH and high UH event days (the red shades). However, the modeled results do not show substantial difference over Mumbai despite having high helicity values as reported in Table 2.2. The CALIPSO pass near Mumbai shows a similar result lofting pollutant up to 2 km from the surface (Fig. 2.9.1). We further analysed BC1 (hydrophobic BC) and BC2 (hydrophilic BC) loading for Mumbai. The WRF Chem emission pre-processor partitions total BC emissions into 80% BC1 and 20% BC2. In the model, BC1 is transformed into BC2 using the fixed ageing rate of 2.5 days in the MOZCART scheme. Thus, BC1 can be viewed as freshly emitted local BC while BC2 can be thought of as an aged local air mass or air transported from elsewhere. The analysis of high UH and low UH days for BC1 over Mumbai shows significant vertical transport while there is little difference in BC2 concentration in both the event days. Thus, it seems that the Mumbai region had high columnar aged air mass during these days, which then lead to very little difference in the total BC loading over the region. Lucknow shows substantial

difference in the BC vertical profile despite having a low helicity value. Our analysis reveals that both BC1 and BC2 contribute similarly to total BC loading over Lucknow. Similar contributions from BC1 and BC2 are seen over Kathmandu except that the total difference in BC loading is smaller than in the case of Lucknow for high and low UH days. However, the Kathmandu region had lower total BC concentrations than that for the IGP region (Lucknow). The analysis of BC lofting with UH data indicates that the UH value alone is not enough to explain vertical transport and distribution. However, higher helicity event days can transport $\sim 1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ BC above 850 hPa (\sim free troposphere).

Similarly, Fig. 2.10 shows the difference in BC vertical transport and distribution for high and low CAPE event days. CAPE is an indication of strong convective motion that contains an updraft and downdraft within the supercell unlike helicity. High CAPE events can influence more horizontal grids in comparison with helicity events. Table 2.2 reports that the highest CAPE difference is over Kolkata, with values reaching up to 4895 J/Kg. The Kolkata subplot in Fig. 2.10 clearly shows the vertical transport of BC crossing 850 hPa (note the red shades) during high CAPE days, which is further observed by CALIPSO (Fig. 2.10.1). Kathmandu and Lucknow also show significant vertical transport of BC crossing 850 hPa despite having much lower CAPE values than that of Kolkata. Similar observations from CALIPSO near Lucknow show pollutant transport up to 5 km (Fig. 2.10.2). As with UH days, Mumbai does not show clear vertical transport with high CAPE values. We also analysed BC1 and BC2 concentrations for CAPE cases and noticed that BC2 contributes significantly to vertical transport during high CAPE days over Kathmandu and Lucknow while BC1 contributes more over the Kolkata region.

We further analysed the contribution of open fires to total BC loading during high and low UH and CAPE event days. We found that total BC concentration is reduced over

Kolkata, Kathmandu and Lucknow when analysing simulation with and without fires, but the results do not show a significant difference in the overall structure or transport pattern when CAPE cases are analysed. The Mumbai region does not show the influence of fires on BC loading during CAPE event days. However, similar results are obtained for the four regions during high and low UH event days.

Fig. 2.9. BC surface concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) for low/high Helicity based case study over selected cities above ground level (agl). (a/b) are low helicity cases with longitude/latitude fixed. (c/d) are high helicity cases with longitude/latitude fixed.

Fig. 2.9.1: Helicity for Mumbai, box shows area of observation from CALIPSO which falls near to model simulated grids for Mumbai.

Fig. 2.10. BC concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) for low/high CAPE based case study over the selected cities above ground level. (a/b) are low CAPE cases with longitude/latitude fixed. (c/d) are high CAPE cases with longitude/latitude fixed.

Fig. 2.10.1: CAPE for Kolkata, box shows area of observation from CALIPSO which falls near to model simulated grids for Kolkata.

Fig. 2.10.2: CAPE for Lucknow, Box shows area of observation from CALIPSO which falls near to model simulated grids for Lucknow.

We further examined BC concentration over these cities (singular grid point) at 850 and 500 hPa for low-high CAPE and UH days. For the days mentioned in Table 2.2, cities show a 167-438% increase in total BC concentration at 850 hPa during high UH days when compared with low UH days. Mumbai, Kolkata and Lucknow show higher BC1 concentration at 850 hPa compared to BC2 whereas Kathmandu shows the opposite. Further,

at 500 hPa, the BC2 concentration is more than BC1 for all four cities although the total BC concentration during high UH days remains 109-400% higher.

The total BC concentration increased by 130-462% at 850 hPa during the high CAPE days compared to low CAPE days (Table 2.3). Mumbai and Kolkata show higher BC1 concentrations at 850 hPa while Lucknow and Kathmandu show higher BC2 concentrations. At 500 hPa, the total BC increased by 194% and 127% over Mumbai and Kolkata, respectively, while Lucknow and Kathmandu show 45-25% lower values. Mumbai (singular grid point) shows a significant increase in total BC concentration at 850 hPa and 500 hPa though it is not evident in the qualitative analysis presented when discussing Fig. 2.9 and 2.10.

Table 2.3. Dates of Helicity and CAPE based cases with values.

City (latitude, longitude)	Helicity cases (Relative %)				CAPE cases (Relative %)			
	850 hPa (Total BC)		500 hPa (Total BC)		850 hPa (Total BC)		500 hPa (Total BC)	
	BC1	BC2	BC1	BC2	BC1	BC2	BC1	BC2
Mumbai (19.08°N,72.88°E)	469		244		116		177	
	2500	377	300	237	122	115	150	185
Kolkata (22.57°N,88.36°E)	212		120		292		57	
	330	142	100	125	742	180	50	55
Kathmandu (27.72°N,85.32°E)	157		280		308		55	
	136	233	200	300	231	383	100	50
Lucknow (26.85°N,80.95°E)	274		400		414		25	
	820	220	NA	350	230	591	NA	28

Our analysis over the cities suggest the lifting of BC above 850 hPa during convection events which is further transported with synoptic monsoon winds towards the central part of India. The central part of the Indian subcontinent shows weak winds during the monsoon period which results in a consistent plume of BC at 500 hPa and above as shown in Fig. 2.6. However, during the pre-monsoon season, uplifted BC gets transported out of the modeling domain by strong westerly winds.

2.4. Conclusions

Our study used the WRF-Chem simulations for the ENSO neutral year 2013 with several sensitivity runs to understand the vertical transport of black carbon over South Asia during the active convection period (i.e., the pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons). The lightning climatology obtained from TRMM lightning dataset from 1995 to 2014 suggests that the pre-monsoon and early monsoon periods are the active convective time over South Asia. The results suggest variation in convection intensity and occurrence within South Asia. The model-simulated BC surface concentration over South Asia, although underestimated, shows good seasonal trends in comparison with the observations. Over the central Himalayan cities like Kathmandu, Nainital and Dehradun, the model simulations did not reproduce observed seasonal trends, particularly during the pre-monsoon season. While previous modeling studies attribute this deficiency to uncertainty in the emission inventory over the region, this analysis suggests that the inverted trend during the pre-monsoon season is due to the dominant role of synoptic atmospheric dynamics along with uncertainty in emission inventories. Thus, future modeling studies would need to improve the parameterizations related to pollutant advection over the central part of the Himalayas to improve model performance.

Time series analysis for different cities and seasonal analysis over the simulation domain at various pressure levels (surface, 850 hPa, 500 hPa and 300 hPa) show vertical transport of BC during pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons. A persistent layer of BC plumes during the monsoon season is observed at 500 hPa and above over the central part of South Asia. The presence of elevated BC can affect atmospheric stability by absorbing radiation, even as its consistent presence may affect monsoon moisture flux by blocking the radiation. While several studies have reported on the elevated BC layer over India during the pre-monsoon season with implications for the monsoon, this study, to our knowledge, is the first to identify a persistent BC plume over central India during the monsoon season. However, as our model results underestimate observed surface BC over the region, it is expected that it may have under-estimated or contained a significant difference in the upper layer BC concentration also. Future studies could focus on the impact of this layer in modulating monsoon and precipitation patterns over South Asia.

To understand BC lofting to free troposphere, we studied several cases. We identified days with high CAPE or helicity in order to examine the contribution of dynamical forcing in lifting BC from the surface to FT. During these high convective periods, BC is easily transported to FT from the surface but not much higher, i.e., only up to UTLS. During the monsoon season, the presence of weaker winds above 500 hPa over the central part of India contributes to a persistent BC layer. Most of the previous studies that show elevated pollutant layers over South Asia, the Himalayas and the Tibetan Plateau focus either on surface layers or on UTLS. This study, however, illustrates that while BC concentration is enhanced in the FT during the convective period, the uplifted BC usually gets advected off from South Asia by strong westerlies. However, although the surface is cleaner during the monsoon due to convective processes and wet removal of BC, the FT from 850 hPa and

above shows significant BC concentration. Thus, the feature identified in our study needs to be further explored in future studies for its possible impact on the South Asian monsoon.

While surface observations of BC and other pollutants are increasing over South Asia, they are still not readily available for robust model performance evaluation. Vertical profiles of pollutant concentrations of primary aerosols such as BC over the region are few with only very limited airborne and balloon-based measurements carried out in the region. While satellite derived products provide some insight into model predictions, there is a need for in-situ measurements of BC concentration aloft over South Asia to further constrain model performance and improve understanding of BC transport to FT. Given the importance of aerosols in modulating the South Asian monsoon, it is critical to understand the vertical profile of pollutant concentrations, not only during the pre-monsoon season but also during the monsoon season.

Chapter 3: Carbonaceous aerosol from open burning and its impact on regional weather in South Asia²

3.1 Background

In this chapter we tried to quantify BC effect on radiation and weather along with OC aerosols. Generally, BC and OC together refer as carbonaceous aerosol (CA). OC and BC together play an important role in weather and climate systems of the atmosphere [132,133]. Major components of carbonaceous aerosol come from anthropogenic activities/sources [95,134–136]. During specific months, loading of a significant amount of carbonaceous aerosol in the atmosphere originates from open biomass burning [84,85,137–144]. Carbonaceous aerosol from open biomass burning are co-emitted along with both long and short lived climate forcers such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), reactive nitrogen (NO_x, NO_y, PANs, and HNO₃) etc. [145–149]. Emissions from biomass burning in South East Asia uplift up to ~3 km [150], similar uplifting of OBB emission were reported over Africa [151] and Amazonia [143].

BC (hydrophobic) strongly absorbs radiation and makes a direct impact by heating the atmospheric column, whereas aged BC (hydrophilic) contributes to ice nucleation (IC) in clouds [22,100,152]. Hydrophobic OC can scatter as well as absorb small fraction of the radiation and create a cooling effect, while aged OC (hydrophilic) acts as a cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) [132,152,153]. Climate forcing over snow and ice due to carbonaceous aerosol deposition have also been reported in previous studies [22,56].

² This chapter is adapted from “Carbonaceous aerosol from open burning and its impact on regional weather in South Asia” P. Singh, P. Sarawade, B. Adhikary, Aerosol and Air Quality Research (2019) (IF=2.78).

Presence of absorbing aerosol such as BC near clouds can evaporate clouds by heating it [154,155]. Results from the recently carried out Precipitation Driver Response Model Inter-comparison Project (PDRMIP) suggests climate forcing from BC affects precipitation outside of the emission source region [156]. Previous studies indicate ~1 K temperature change near to surface can alter the water vapor content by ~5% [157,158].

Current understanding of emissions of carbonaceous aerosol from open burning shows two regional hot spots relevant to South Asia [144,146,159]. They are the Indo Gangetic Plains (IGP), and Southeast Asia in and around Myanmar. Amongst the Asian countries, Myanmar is known as the biggest source of forest fires during the months of March and April [133,160]. Emissions from agricultural residue (biomass) burning over Myanmar in both dry and wet seasons is much lower compared to forest fires [139,146,161]. Crop residue burning during April-May and October-November over IGP causes a serious air quality problem, especially in October-November when planetary boundary layer (PBL) is low [162–164]. Over South Asia (Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar, Nepal, and Pakistan), BC emission from non-agricultural open fire is ~11.62 Gg/year whereas OC emission is estimated as ~106.17 Gg/year [139]. Total emission from open biomass burning (OBB) is estimated at BC ~150Gg and OC ~1151Gg for South Asia [165].

Local and regional pollution events due to forest fires and agricultural biomass burning are reported in earlier studies [149,166]. Most of the previous studies were limited to characterization and estimation of emission from OBB (forest and crop residue burning) [133,139,159]. Some of the studies over South East Asia were limited to transport of emissions from OBB with implications to urban and regional air quality [138,167]. Recently studies simulate climatic effects of hypothetical 10x-BC (anthropogenic BC emission was increased by a factor of 10) on regional weather and climate [156,158]. This study investigates a case of high carbonaceous aerosol (BC+OC) in the atmosphere emitted from

OBB and its impact on the weather during pre and post monsoon over South Asia. While the hypothetical high BC emission case studies were carried out using a global chemistry-climate model, we tried to understand the impact of high BC emission using a high-resolution regional weather forecasting model coupled with chemistry (WRF-Chem) in this study. We do not prescribe a hypothetical carbonaceous aerosol emission rather understand the impact with estimated increase in carbonaceous aerosol emissions regardless of the magnitude. Results from two different OBB inventories are analysed over SA indicating the difference in emission strength. Vertical concentration of carbonaceous aerosol is presented over South Asia as prior studies [168,169] have indicated the importance of vertical profile of BC on its radiative forcing. And finally, the impact of carbonaceous aerosol on regional weather is discussed along with the impact on various meteorological parameters.

3.2 Observation and Methodology:

3.2.1 Fire Observations:

Information from monthly gridded Global Fire Emissions Database (version 4.1) (GFED4s) from 1997 to 2015 is used for analysis [170]. This data set is available at 0.25° resolution and was downloaded from https://daac.ornl.gov/cgi-bin/dsviewer.pl?ds_id=1293 . This set of data provides total carbon ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$) and dry matter ($\text{kg DM m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$) emissions from open fire globally. Emissions from different sources such as grassland and savanna, woodland, deforested and degraded areas, forests, from agricultural waste burning, and peat fires are included. MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) burned area map along with TRMM (Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission), VIRS (Visible and Infrared Scanner) and ATSR (Along-Track Scanning Radiometer) data were used to generate this GFED data set [170].

Fire Inventory from NCAR (version 1.0) (FINNv1) available at 1 km resolution was also used in this study [31]. This dataset was downloaded from <http://bai.acom.ucar.edu/Data/fire/>. This set of data contains trace gas and particle emissions from various sources of open burning like wildfire, agricultural fires, and managed burnings [31]. MODIS Rapid Response data was used to identify fire location and time for FINN data set.

Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS) Global Fire Assimilation System (GFAS) data set is also used in this study. The dataset is downloaded from <https://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/data/cams-gfas/>. CAMS-GFAS data set contains wildfire flux of ~40 species at the 0.1° spatial resolution at a daily resolution. MODIS generated fire radiative power is used in GFAS to generate emission product [171]. CAMS-GFAS data for the months of March, April, October and November of 2013 are used in analysis.

CALIPSO (Cloud-Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observation) uses active lidar and passive infrared sensors to measure vertical profile of the atmosphere. CALIPSO images from https://www-calipso.larc.nasa.gov/products/lidar/browse_images/production/ were used to understand fire emissions from the available satellite overpass during the active biomass burning events in this study. Specifically, CALIPSO level 1 version 3.3 data with air pollution speciation (clean marine, dust, polluted continental, clean continental, polluted dust and smoke) was used in this study.

3.2.2 Chemical Transport Model:

WRF-Chem (version 3.8.1) (Weather Research Forecasting model) is used for this study [24,25]. Fig. 3.1 shows model domain projected on Mercator projection centred at 22°N, 78°E which covers from 6.5°-36.0°N and 53.0°-103.0°E on a spatial resolution of 25

km. The model contains 40 vertical levels, height of first 10 levels are within 300 m each and above all levels are within 650 m each.

Emission Database from Global Atmospheric Research- Hemispheric Transport of Air Pollution (EDGAR-HTAP) offers anthropogenic emission at $0.1^{\circ} \times 0.1^{\circ}$ spatial resolution for the year 2010 [83]. We used the EDGAR-HTAP emissions in this study using pre-processor tool available from NCAR website [27]. The time-varying initial and boundary condition from the Model for Ozone and Related chemical Tracers, version 4 (Mozart-4) is used in this study [32]. O_2 and O_3 column densities from `exo_coldens` is used for photolysis processes in MOZART/MOZCART option in WRF-Chem simulation. Monthly biogenic flux from the Model of Emissions of Gases and Aerosols from Nature (version 2.1) (MEGAN2.1) used in this WRF-Chem simulation [29]. Daily sea surface temperature (SST) was updated in model simulation using data from (<http://polar.ncep.noaa.gov/mrab/translation.shtml>).

Model simulation for this study use MOZCART chemistry, which is combination of MOZART model (trace gas chemistry) and Goddard Chemistry Aerosol Radiation and Transport (GOCART) model (bulk aerosols chemistry). Dust emission is selected as of GOCART chemistry provided with fractional erosion map, Dimethyl sulfide (DMS) emissions is kept active [94].

Simulation for this study incorporates emission estimate from the Fire INventory from NCAR model version1 (FINNv1) which provides daily open burning emission at $1 \text{ km} \times 1 \text{ km}$ spatial resolution (<https://www2.acom.ucar.edu/modeling/finn-fire-inventory-ncar>) [31]. Both smouldering and flaming emissions are included in the mapped data set. MOZCART based biomass burning emission and plume rise calculation is used for FINNv1 data as mentioned above. Parameterization detail is provided in Table 3.1.

3.2.3 Methodology:

FINN and GFED monthly biomass burning carbonaceous emission from 1997 to 2015 was used to identify and analyse fire hot spots over South Asia (6.5° - 36.0° N, 53.0° - 103.0° E). Based on GFED and FINN, Punjab (28.83° - 32.01° N, 72.91° - 77.86° E) and Myanmar (13.86° - 27.74° N, 90.28° - 102.69° E) are located as hot spots for biomass burning. Given the temporal and spatial similarity of fires, this study only used FINN fire emissions for further analysis. The fire_emis source code from NCAR site is used to map all FINN data set from 2002 to 2015 on hourly file.

Two sets of year-long simulations with WRF-Chem model are carried out for 2013. First set of simulations are carried out with total emissions (anthropogenic + OBB) of all air pollutants including carbonaceous species. While the second experiment is simulated by omitting only carbonaceous aerosol from OBB. In both the model simulations, National Centers for Environmental Prediction Final Analysis (NCEP FNL) data is used to update initial and boundary meteorological condition. To preserve similar meteorology in both simulations and avoiding divergence in meteorological parameters; simulations were reinitialized every day with NCEP FNL data. Whereas chemistry was carried forward from the last step of every previous day simulation to maintain consistency in the vertical and horizontal concentration of chemical species. Chemical boundary condition is updated using MOZART output for each time step. This algorithm was followed in both simulations throughout the year that maintains meteorology and chemistry consistent. WRF-Chem simulations of meteorology and chemistry are compared in detail in various previous studies [27,70].

Table 3.1: *WRF-chem Model Parameterization option used in this study.*

Parameterization	Scheme	Reference
Bulk microphysical parameterization	Thompson scheme	[86]
Convective parameterization	Kain–Fritsch Scheme	[87]
Planetary boundary layer (PBL)	Yonsei University Scheme	[88]
Shortwave radiation physics	Dudhia Shortwave Scheme	[89]
Longwave radiation physics	RRTM Longwave Scheme	[90]
Land-atmosphere interaction	Unified Noah Land Surface Model scheme	[91]
Surface layer option	MM5	[92]
Photolysis	Madronich fast-Ultraviolet-Visible Model (F-TUV)	[93]

3.3 Results and Discussion:

Averaged total carbon emissions ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$) from biomass burning using GFED4 from 1997 to 2015 is shown in Fig. 3.1a. Burning over Myanmar shows the highest carbonaceous emission within the domain. Carbonaceous emissions due to biomass burning from Punjab (Pakistan and India) to Bihar (India) also show elevated emissions. Apart from Myanmar and Punjab (IGP), Fig. 3.1(a) also shows biomass burning emission over Western Ghats (WG), Eastern Ghats (EG) and Sri Lanka. Fig. 3.1(b), shows biomass burning carbonaceous aerosol emission ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$) from FiNN data set averaged for the period of 2002 to 2015. Despite differences in input data sets (MODIS/VIIRS/TRMM etc.) both

FiNN and GFED4 identify similar features within Myanmar and Punjab as hotspot regions. The CAMS dataset for 2013 (Fig. 3.1c) shows similar features illustrating 2013 as a normal year at least in spatial emission patterns when compared to climatology datasets. All three data use similar kind of satellite observation data set, but the different algorithm to define the area of coverage and emissions from open biomass burning.

Fig. 3.1: Long term average of carbonaceous aerosol emission from open biomass burning (OBB): (a) GFED monthly average total carbon emission from 1997-2015, (b) FINN average carbonaceous (Black + Organic) aerosol emission rates from 2002-2015, (c) Area averaged carbonaceous (Black + Organic) aerosol emission from CAMS and (d) Climatology of carbonaceous aerosol (Black + Organic) from FINN model for Punjab and Myanmar regions.

Myanmar biomass burning episodes are mostly contribution from forest fires during dry and hot days of the pre-monsoon season [133,160,172]. Punjab biomass burning is a result of agricultural crop residue burning in April-May when the wheat crop is harvested, and during October-November when rice crop is harvested [159,163,173]. October-November biomass burning over Punjab is often in news and media reports because of deteriorating air quality situation in the IGP [162,164,174]. March and April months emission are under less scrutiny due to the convectively active season which transports the pollutants in the vertical layers compared to the winter season [133].

Further, area averaged OBB emissions from Punjab (28.83° - 32.01° N, 72.91° - 77.86° E) and Myanmar (13.86° - 27.74° N, 90.28° - 102.69° E), for the period of January 2002 to December 2015 (presented in Fig. 3.1d). Fig. 3.1d shows a single fire season over Myanmar starting from February and continuing till the onset of the monsoons. March is recorded as the highest OBB in Myanmar followed by April and February. Unlike Myanmar, Punjab shows two biomass burning seasons, the first in April-May and second in October-November. Table 3.2 shows the emission strength from open burning within these two model subdomains compared to anthropogenic emissions. Results in the parenthesis show lean burning seasons; March-April for Punjab and October-November for Myanmar. Analysis of emissions during active fire seasons reveals that Punjab emissions increase approximately 83-106% compared to anthropogenic emissions from FINN model (~26-50% from CAMS) while Myanmar emissions increase by 2338-3054% from the FINN model (476-735% from CAMS). These results show real-world example of 10X BC climate simulations as carried out by the PDRMIP studies but applicable to current weather timescales.

Table 3.2: *Comparison of carbonaceous aerosol emission with anthropogenic emissions and different fire emission model estimates.*

Region	Anthropogenic (g/m ² /month) (BC+OC)	FINN Emission (g/m ² /month) (BC+OC)	CAMS (g/m ² /month) (BC+OC)	GFED Emission (g/m ² /month) (carbon emissions)
Myanmar	0.03	0.62-0.81 (0.0011-0.0019)	0.13-0.19 (0.0002-0.0005)	9.91-12.71 (0.0319-0.0775)
Punjab	0.11	0.091-0.12 (0.0019-0.0038)	0.03-0.05 (0.0001-0.0013)	1.59-5.59 (0.044-0.2250)

Given the uncertainty of the emissions from biomass burning [31,170,171], we proceed further analysis with FINN model emissions to estimate the impact on weather. The simulations include biomass burning emissions and plume rise calculation for MOZCART (biomass_burn_opt=2). The model considers the fire emission as surface emission in the simulation, whereas injection height of OBB emission depends on the stability of the atmosphere and vertical winds [175,176]. Generally, injection height shows a strong diurnal cycle depends on PBL stability, varies 2-3 km in height which is usually above the PBL [177]. As discussed in the model setup section height of each vertical level (first 10 levels) in the model simulation are less than 300m, to capture stability and mixing in PBL layers. Whereas the height of vertical levels above PBL (mostly 11th level onwards) are below 650m. Solely injection height of OBB emission strongly depends on thermodynamic stability and PBL dynamics. Whereas uncertainty related to PBL height and thermal stability can affect the vertical distribution of BC. The GFED files available on monthly time scales but too coarse of a temporal resolution to assess its impact on weather, while CAMS emissions were much lower than FINN to pick up significant alteration on weather variables. Further results and discussions are limited to March-April for Myanmar, and October November for Punjab region.

Fig. 3.2 shows vertical BC concentration area average for Myanmar (March-April 2013) and Punjab (October-November). Fig. 3.2a shows model simulations of BC concentration over Myanmar from the control run which includes biomass burning while Fig.

3.2b shows the concentration without biomass burning emissions. Similarly, Figs. 3.2(c and d) shows BC concentration from the control run and simulation without biomass burning emissions for Punjab region. Fig. 3.2a shows significantly higher surface and boundary layer BC concentration when compared to Fig. 3.2b. Similar results are present in Figs. 3.2c-d. Fig. 3.2d shows that BC concentrations are very high (black colour scale) for few days in mid-October to mid-November indicating that significant emissions from Punjab region are limited to few days and not spread throughout the post-monsoon period. CALIPSO passes over Myanmar shows most of the days in March and April consist of smoke up to 5 km (Fig. 3.2.1); whereas passes over Punjab during October-November shows presence of smoke below 3 km (Fig. 3.2.2). Similar smoke plume height is reported over India and South East Asia in previous study [133,178]. Organic Carbon concentration over Myanmar and Punjab show similar trends and spatial distribution albeit at higher concentration than BC.

Fig. 3.2: Area averaged BC concentration (a) Myanmar control run (b) Myanmar without OBB BC (c) Punjab control run and (d) Punjab without OBB BC.

While Fig. 3.2 showed sub-domain (Punjab and Myanmar) averaged vertical profile of BC, Fig. 3.3 shows difference in plots of monthly averaged BC concentration between the control and no OBB simulations at different vertical layers indicating the horizontal spread of BC aerosol. Rows illustrate concentration differences over several months, while columns report vertical levels. At the surface, during March and April, differences in BC concentration in and around Myanmar shows a north south gradient. Elevated concentration differences are also seen along the eastern India shoreline in the Bay of Bengal. At 850 hPa which is near to PBL, results show similar features as the surface. Surface and 850 hPa results show that BC emitted from OBB during March and April fires affect mostly the eastern and southern part of the domain. Further, at 500 and 300 hPa differences in BC concentration is still shown by the model, although diminishing over Bay of Bengal at the 300 hPa.

Fig. 3.2.1: CALIPSO pass over Myanmar region during open biomass burning period.

Fig. 3.2.2: CALIPSO pass over Punjab region during open biomass burning period.

Fig. 3.3: Atmospheric loading of BC from OBB (a) at the Surface, (b) 850 hPa, (c) 500 hPa, (d) 300 hPa.

Similarly, the third and fourth row in Fig. 3.3 shows monthly averaged differences in BC concentration for October and November respectively. At the surface, results show

prominent features around Punjab region with a sharp north to south gradient. The difference in concentration between the two simulations is not as strong over the entire domain as compared to fires from the Myanmar region. 850 hPa subplot shows similar features as the surface with lower magnitude. Weak northerly winds over surface and 850 hPa prevents dispersal of BC concentration towards the northern portion of the modeling domain. Small amounts of BC concentration from OBB is observed over the Tibetan Plateau (TP) at 500 hPa whereas 300 hPa remains clean. Similar trends for OC at surface, 850 hPa, 500 hPa and 300 hPa is observed for all the four months (Fig. 3.3.1), observed OC concentration is much higher ($\sim 4\times$) than BC. Such amount of BC and OC at surface and column levels can affect the incoming shortwave and outgoing long wave radiation budget, which may feedback into local meteorology [95].

Fig. 3.3.1: Atmospheric loading of OC from open biomass burning at the Surface, 850 hPa, 500 hPa, 300 hPa.

Table 3.3 shows the area-averaged impact of carbonaceous aerosol from OBB on incoming shortwave and outgoing longwave flux over the entire modeling domain and within the source regions. Our results show outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) flux reduces by 0.28 W/m^2 over the entire modeling domain while it further reduced by 1.91 W/m^2 over the source region. Top of the atmosphere (TOA) BC forcing was reported to be $\pm 1 \text{ W/m}^2$ by Ramanathan et al., (2005) over South Asia [179]. Whereas Chung et al., (2010) suggest -4.2 W/m^2 TOA radiative forcing due to anthropogenic aerosol, BC radiative forcing is reported $+2.1 \text{ W/m}^2$ for Asia which is similar to our results [168]. Similar observation-based results from India suggest surface forcing -23 W/m^2 and TOA forcing of 5 W/m^2 by enhanced BC over the urban environment [180]. Variation within the two months shows the sensitivity of forcing based on the emissions and subsequent concentrations.

Table 3.3: Radiative forcing from OBB carbonaceous aerosol over Myanmar and Punjab.

Region	Month	Domain area average effect		Local area average effect	
		Surface incoming short wave flux(W/m^2)	TOA outgoing longwave wave flux(W/m^2)	Surface incoming short wave flux(W/m^2)	TOA outgoing longwave wave flux(W/m^2)
Myanmar (13.86° - 27.74° N, 90.28° - 102.69° E)	March	-8.05	-0.28	-42.76	-1.91
	April	-6.78	-0.1	-29.16	-0.52
Punjab (28.83° - 32.04° N, 72.91° - 77.86° E)	October	-0.45	-0.02	-5.13	-0.48
	November	-1.34	-0.06	-6.14	-0.50

Sharma et al., (2010) reported total surface radiative flux of -134 W/m^2 to -212 W/m^2 and TOA radiative flux -41 W/m^2 to -47 W/m^2 over Punjab for the month of October (2006-2007) [164]. Our study estimates changes in OLR flux over Punjab to be $\sim -0.48 \text{ W/m}^2$ for the entire region. Model reports area averaged surface forcing to be 0.008 to -78.21 W/m^2 and OLR at TOA to be -4.96 to 2.48 W/m^2 over Punjab comparable to the observations. Regional

BC radiative forcing in the 1990s at the surface was estimated to be between -30 W/m^2 to -20 W/m^2 over northern BoB [169,179,181] and total aerosol forcing of $\sim -75 \text{ W/m}^2$ was reported during the same time period [182]. Surface radiative forcing reported due to anthropogenic aerosol is -8.6 W/m^2 and -5.2 W/m^2 by BC over Asia [168]. Our results provide insight into the contribution of carbonaceous aerosol which has similar emission sources and patterns, unlike the previous studies that either focus on a single aerosol or total aerosol effect. Our result shows carbonaceous aerosols from open biomass burning strongly alter radiation balance in the atmosphere at a local and regional level.

Carbonaceous aerosols from OBB shows a strong influence on surface incoming shortwave flux over Myanmar and Punjab (Table 3.3), which indicates less radiation is reaching to surface. Such a strong reduction in radiation at the surface, make a negative change in temperature, which is further justified in Fig. 3.4, where the temperature drops significantly as well as other factors also change. Similar results are presented by Ding et al., (2013) over China where the temperature drops up to 10K is reported during OBB and high pollution events[183].

Fig. 3.4: Effect of OBB carbonaceous aerosol concentration (a-b), impact on 2m relative humidity (c-d), 2m-Temperature (e-f), PBL height (g-h) and 10m wind speed (i-j) for Myanmar and Punjab respectively.

Fig. 3.4 depicts domain averaged OBB carbonaceous aerosol impact on surface weather parameters over from Punjab and Myanmar. Figs. 3.4a-b show the time series of OBB- carbonaceous aerosol concentration while the rest show changes in meteorological parameters. Results show that changes are proportional to surface concentration. Lower concentration of carbonaceous aerosol from fire over both Myanmar and Punjab do not make significant impacts on the meteorological parameters. Wind speed (Figs. 3.4c-d) shows both positive and negative changes, RH (Figs. 3.4e-f) shows increase in values while temperature (Figs. 3.4g-h) and PBL (Figs. 3.4i-j) height show decrease in magnitude. Magnitude of surface temperature change is up to 2K. RH values change by up to 8%. Increase in relative

humidity (RH) is due to high moist static energy during biomass burning events, during this period high evaporation rate [184] and shallow PBL height results into higher RH [183]. Magnitude of wind speed is altered by -0.6 to 0.3 m/s with decreasing wind speed majority of the time. PBL height significantly changes in 200-600 m.

Krishnan and Ramanathan, (2002) suggest 10-15% increase in BC concentration can block up to 10% solar radiation which leads to 0.3° C cooling at surface [181]. Further they note that the observed cooling may lead to warming elsewhere. Up to 8% increase in relative humidity is suggested during polluted period [185]. Balachandran et al., (2017) reported fire PM_{2.5} had inverse relationship with variables like PBL and wind speed like our results [186].

Fig. 3.5 shows temperature difference (monthly average) due to OBB emitted carbonaceous aerosol at different vertical layers. Given higher difference in OBB carbonaceous aerosol concentration over Myanmar compared to Punjab, the changes in surface and 850 hPa temperature is stronger over Myanmar than Punjab. Small rises in temperature is seen over the north western domain during the month of April and over Eastern portion of the domain in November possibly due to changed circulation. Smaller temperature changes are simulated over the entire domain during the month of April at 500 hPa and 300 hPa, while other months show very little or localized change at these altitudes. Balachandran et al., (2017) and Saha et al., (2014) have also reported changes in PBL and other meteorological variables due to aerosol radiative feedback which could lead to warming elsewhere [186,187]. Finally, our study suggests that carbonaceous aerosol (BC + OC) together also reduce surface temperature like BC despite scattering effects of organic carbon.

Fig. 3.5: Effect carbonaceous aerosol from OBB on temperature at different pressure level (a) Surface (b) 850 hPa (c) 500 hPa and (d) 300 hPa.

We also examined the impact of OBB carbonaceous aerosol on precipitation amount and pattern over South Asia. OBB over south Asia occurs during pre-monsoon and post-monsoon, a period when there isn't significant precipitation over the continent. Previous studies have reported on the impact of aerosols, especially BC on changes in monsoon precipitation later during the season [66]. In this study, we analysed fast response to precipitation amount and pattern. Our results indicate that there is no significant change in either amount or pattern of precipitation over the modeling domain, ~2-5% change is simulated near Myanmar and is limited to a few grids (Fig. 3.5.1.). We wish to point out that the study only considered direct effects through radiative forcing and did not examine the aerosol cloud interaction and pathways for changes in precipitation. PDRMIP multi-model

study also suggested effect of 10×BC on Asian precipitation is very less (~1.4%) [156] similar to this study results.

Fig. 3.5.1: *Precipitation rate during OBB period with control run and experiment run and difference in precipitation rate in respective months.*

3.4 Summary and Conclusion:

Climatology from GFED4 and FINN fire products report Punjab and Myanmar as major contributors of carbonaceous aerosol emissions from open biomass burning along with some smaller emissions sources from Western Ghats and Eastern Ghats in South Asia. Major

contribution of open biomass burning emissions in South Asia comes from Myanmar forest fires, which occurs during March-April when the weather is dry and hot. During April, along with Myanmar, many other areas near the Eastern Ghats and Western Ghats and southern part of Nepal show biomass burning. However, emission from these areas are very less compared to Myanmar. April-May and October-November are agricultural residue burning periods over the Punjab region. Agricultural residue burning during both pre-monsoon and post- monsoon is limited to 10-15 days with differing dates based on agricultural harvest periods.

Area averaged time series vertical profile of carbonaceous aerosol concentration shows that bulk of the aerosol are lofted to 3-5 km. Specific events transport plumes higher, and concentrations are simulated to reach up to 300 hPa. Plume vertical transport completely depends on PBL mixing and thermodynamic stability in the atmosphere. During Myanmar fire (March-April) PBL is high and due to active convection in that region, more vertical transport is visible. Whereas over Punjab (October-November) PBL is shallower than the rest of season and atmosphere is stable, very less vertical transport is evident. Uncertainty in PBL height and thermodynamic parameterization may affect the vertical plume height of OBB emission and transport. PBL aerosol feedback also can affect the concentration at the lower levels. Shallower PBL may reduce dispersion which leads to higher aerosol concentration whereas high PBL helps in mixing aerosol and more dispersion is possible which may reduce significant concentration in PBL. Radiative forcing calculations show that carbonaceous aerosol over Punjab contributed to -6.14 W/m^2 at the surface and -0.50 W/m^2 at TOA while over Myanmar results show -42.76 W/m^2 at the surface and -1.91 W/m^2 at TOA. Results are like previous study estimates when compared to BC and total aerosol forcing. This is the first reporting of radiative forcing with combined effects of carbonaceous aerosol (BC +OC) from open fires which contribute to significant loading the in atmosphere during active burning. BC and OC interact with radiation differently, quantifying the effect of BC and OC on

incoming and outgoing radiation flux separately are required in the future study. Carbonaceous aerosols effect on incoming and outgoing radiation flux results into changes in weather parameters such as surface temperature decreased by 2 K, RH changed by 8% and PBL changed up to 600m. Changes in meteorological parameters are proportional to concentrations of carbonaceous aerosol emitted during biomass burning events. Changes in precipitation pattern and amount were negligible due to carbonaceous aerosol from open biomass burning when considering only the direct radiative feedback. Since we had kept anthropogenic emissions and other emissions from fire same as of control run, precipitation changes due to carbonaceous aerosols from open biomass burning are not that evident.

Our study shows similar radiative impact from carbonaceous aerosol from open biomass burning when compared to total impacts from total (anthropogenic + biomass) BC aerosol. The study is limited to impacts of meteorology. This study shows the strong effect of carbonaceous aerosol on local meteorological parameters in a sense which leads to less dispersion of pollutant. Such negative feedback of carbonaceous aerosol on PBL and temperature leads to positive feedback on aerosol concentration. During winter this effect leads to bad pollution events in IGP region. Future studies could explore the impact on circulation patterns and atmospheric composition. Further, the results are based on a year-long study and the results could vary intra-annually. Impacts of precipitation patterns could be further explored with aerosol cloud interaction.

Chapter 4: Role of aerosol in Monsoon extreme precipitation event over Himalayan region using WRF-Chem model at Cloud resolving scale.³

4.1 Background

Chapter 2 and 3 shows presence of aerosols at high altitude, specially BC and their impact on radiation influx and weather. In this chapter we tried to find out relation between aerosols and extreme precipitation events with example of Kedarnath flood case along with other factors. Dimri et al., (2017) reviewed dynamic, thermodynamic and physical reasons of cloud burst cases in Himalayan region, and their impact to society in detail [1]. Generally, interaction of fast moving monsoon with existing active westerlies [2] and orographic uplifting often results havoc in the central Himalayan region [189]. Himalayan foothills make an intersection point where northward moving monsoon, active westerlies and orographic lifting produces high convection and thunderstorm activity [4]. Previous study has indicated that presence of aerosols can enhance or suppress rain over Asian region [5]. Indo Gangetic Plain (IGP) which is known as a hotspot of anthropogenic pollution in South Asia [190] as well as deserts of Rajasthan and middle-east Asia [191] supply ample amount of aerosols to Himalayan region.

Aerosol-Cloud-Precipitation interaction is considered a complex system and much remains to be understood [192–194]. Aerosols act as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN), which is necessary to form cloud and rain [192]. Some of the aerosols act as ice nuclei (IN) [195,196] which may hold the water content in clouds and delay the precipitation [197]. In

³ This chapter is adapted from “Role of aerosol in Monsoon extreme precipitation event over Himalayan region using WRF-Chem model at cloud resolving scale” P. Singh, P. Sarawade, B. Adhikary, *Advances in Atmospheric Sciences* (2020) (In Communication).

the presence of excess aerosols, smaller cloud droplets are formed which reduces the precipitation amount [192]. In the form of CCN and IN in clouds, aerosols affect the cloud properties such as brightness, cloud cover, cloud top temperature and cloud top pressure [22,198,199]. Presence of aerosol layers above or below a cloud can affect the cloud cover in either way [15,16]. Andreae and Rosenfeld (2008) reported that natural aerosol and CCN concentration is lower over land and cloud formation over the continent mostly results from anthropogenic emissions. More CCN (more aerosols) leads to smaller and narrower cloud droplet size and distribution which results into suppressed warm rain and enhanced cold rain. Higher CCN in mix phased cloud makes it deeper and enhances lightning activity with more flashes [200]. Increase of 1-30% dust and sea salt concentration affect the cloud property and precipitation significantly; 15% increase in dust concentration may delay rain by one hour was reported [12]. Up to 70% increase in CCN over northwestern Europe due to aged Saharan dust is reported by Bègue et al., (2015). Increased cloud fraction (~5%) and decreased cloud top pressure (~40mb) is reported due to elevated aerosol concentration over Atlantic [199]. Several studies have indicated that aerosols are not only limited to acting as CCN/IN, but that they also affect radiation derived parameters (such as convective available energy (CAPE) and convective inhibition energy (CIN) important in prediction of severe weather [194,202]. Indian summer monsoon (ISM) is associated with heavy rainfall in most of the areas in South Asia during June-September [14]. Onset of summer monsoon in India is observed between last week of May to first week of June, and the Indian Meteorological Department defines the onset of monsoon as when there is continuous rainfall for more than 5 days over Kerala (a state of India) is observed [16]. Once monsoon touches the southern tip of India, it takes few days to reach rest of India [203]. Till the monsoon is fully developed, northern India receives very less rainfall during the month of June [204].

Most of the extreme precipitation events over western Himalaya are observed during the month of September based on the records available from 1875-2010 [205]. On 16th -17th June 2013, a rapid arrival of monsoon in northern India along with the presence of strong westerlies over the region was one of the major cause for a massive precipitation event over Kedarnath, India [21–23, 45]. Kedarnath (30.73°N, 79.06°E; 3553 m from sea level) is a small town in Indian state of Uttarakhand in the Himalayan region. This study focuses on the atmospheric analysis during the Kedarnath flood which occurred during 16th-17th June 2013, which was followed by significant flooding over western Nepal 17th-18th June 2013, an event which was later called as Himalayan tsunami [206]. Kedarnath floods claimed loss of hundreds of human life and damaged vast infrastructure [204]. Many studies after the event tried to analyze the causes for such devastation. Some of the observation [188,204] and model [207] based studies have analyzed meteorological conditions, orographic and climatic prospective [206,209] and effect of chemistry on precipitation [210].

This study tries to understand the role of aerosols at the synoptic and cloud resolving scales during the Kedarnath heavy precipitation event using state of the art regional Weather Research Forecast coupled with chemistry (WRF-Chem) model. Model horizontal grid resolution of below 5x5km is considered as cloud resolving scale where there is no need of specific cumulus parameterization schemes in the model [211,212]. Additionally, we discuss how the presence of aerosols affected radiation and altered the severe weather indices, which are important in prediction precipitation and severe weather.

4.2. Data and Methodology:

4.2.1. Observations:

Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) monthly level 3 data (TRMM_3A12) available at resolution $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ (https://disc.gsfc.nasa.gov/datacollection/TRMM_3A12_7.html) is used to analyse the general trend over the region of study. Further analysis is performed using TRMM-TMPA (Multi-satellite Precipitation) level 3 data at $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ special resolution available 3 hourly.

In-situ data for various stations obtained from Meteorological & Oceanographic Satellite Data Archival Centre (MOSDAC) of Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) containing precipitation, relative humidity, wind direction and speed, temperature and near surface pressure were used in this study. MOSDAC collects data from Indian Meteorological Department (IMD) and various Automated Weather Station (AWS) from different sources (<https://www.mosdac.gov.in/>). Radio Sounding data set obtain from <http://weather.uwyo.edu/upperair/sounding.html> were used to understand the vertical atmospheric dynamics during the event days, 15th - 20th June 2013.

Atmospheric infrared sounder (AIRS) Aqua level 3 daily product available at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ resolution (AIRX3STD) downloaded from <https://search.earthdata.nasa.gov/> was used to understand the cloud property during heavy precipitation event. Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) level 3 Terra (MOD08_D3) and Aqua (MYD08_D3) daily product available at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ resolution were also used along with AIRS. Both the satellite products provide Cloud fraction, Cloud top pressure and temperature which is useful to understand the cloud properties.

4.2.2. Model configuration

Weather Research Forecasting (WRF) model [82] coupled with chemistry (WRF-Chem,) version 3.8.1 [25] is used in this study to understand the role of aerosols in precipitation. Daily sea surface temperature (SST) was updated in model simulation using data available from (<http://polar.ncep.noaa.gov/mxab/translation.shtml>).

Table 4.1: Domain and parameterization details for different simulations.

Simulations	WC25	WRF25	WC4	WRF4
Centred at	22°N, 78°E		30°N, 80°E	
Resolution	25x25 km		4x4 km	
No. of grids	130 x 203 x 40		223 x 555 x 40	
Domain	6.5°-36.0°N, 53.0°-103.0°E		28°-32.0°N, 74.25°-85.75°E	
Chemistry Scheme	MOZCART	-	MOZCART	-
Bulk microphysical parameterization	Thompson scheme [86]			
Convective parameterization	Kain–Fritsch Scheme [87]			
Planetary boundary layer physics	Yonsei University Scheme (YSU) [88]			
Shortwave radiation physics	Dudhia Shortwave Scheme [89]			
Longwave radiation physics	RRTM Longwave Scheme [90]			
Land-atmosphere interaction	Unified Noah Land Surface Model scheme [91]			

Surface layer option	MM5 Similarity Scheme [92]
Photolysis	Madronich fast-Ultraviolet-Visible Model (F-TUV) [93]

Emission Database for Global Atmospheric Research- Hemispheric Transport of Air Pollution (EDGAR-HTAP) available on $0.1^{\circ} \times 0.1^{\circ}$ spatial resolution [83]. We used EDGAR annual emissions as anthropogenic emission in model using EDGAR-HTAP pre-processor tool available from NCAR website [27]. Fire INventory from NCAR model version1 (FINNv1) which provides daily open burning based emission estimates at $1 \text{ km} \times 1 \text{ km}$ spatial resolution (<https://www2.acom.ucar.edu/modeling/finn-fire-inventory-ncar>) was used in simulation [31].

The modeling framework uses time-varying boundary and initial chemical condition generated from the Model for Ozone and Related chemical Tracers, version 4 (Mozart-4) (<https://www.acom.ucar.edu/wrf-chem/mozart.shtml>). MOZBC utility is used to initiate WRF-Chem simulations. MOZART-4 is offline global chemical transport model which includes 85 trace gases, 12 bulk aerosols with 39 photolysis and 157 gas-phase reactions [32].

4.2.3. Model simulations

Six set of simulations are performed to analyse the effect of bulk aerosols on Himalayan extreme precipitation event. Out of these, three sets of WRF simulations were performed at the resolution of 25 km for the domain consisting whole Indian subcontinent (6.5° - 36.0° N, 53.0° - 103.0° E) with MOZCART, MOZART and without chemistry option. Similarly, the other three sets of WRF simulation were performed at the resolution of 4 km covering area in south starting from Indo Gangetic Plan (IGP) to Himalayan Mountains (28° - 32.0° N, 74.25° - 85.75° E). One week spin up time was used to stabilize the chemistry in the model and no nesting was used in simulation. Further analysis was carried out using the data

from 3 days before to 3 days after the event, after the spin up period. WRF simulations with MOZCART chemistry and without chemistry at 25 km (WC25 and WRF25 respectively) and 4 km (WC4 and WRF4 respectively) are discussed further in detail. Similar chemistry background is used in all the simulations to maintain the consistency. All the parameterizations were used in simulation as per Table 4.1.

4.3. Results and Discussion:

4.3.1. Climatology

Normal rain was reported during monsoon 2013 throughout India, except few states of India like Bihar, Arunachal Pradesh and Jammu [208], whereas June 2013 was reported with excess rain over most of the India, except north-east India [208]. Uttarakhand faced more than 191% excess rain during the month of June, which was highest compared to any other state, while overall monsoon recorded only 12% excess rain. As per IMD records, more than 13 districts of Uttarakhand recorded excess rain during June 2013 which was an unusual event in the month of June [206].

This study used TRMM monthly surface rain rate data product (TRMM_3A12) from January 1998 to December 2014 to understand the rain pattern in Uttarakhand, a state of India, and over Kedarnath, the Himalayan Mountain city. The year 2013 was a neutral year in terms of El-Niño nor La-Nina. Analysis of seasonal and annual average precipitation over Uttarakhand for the year 2013 suggested that it was an average year in terms of accumulated precipitation when compared to other years from 1998-2014. On the other hand, monthly analysis suggested that in 2013, the month of June observed highest precipitation compared to any other year. Area averaged rain rate taken from few horizontal grids over Kedarnath

suggests that seasonal and annual rain rate for the year 2013 was average during the analysis period, whereas rain rate was higher compared to the state of Uttarakhand. Kedarnath grid suggests rain rate during the month of June and monsoon of 2013 was highest compared to any other year from 1998-2014. Fig. 4.1 shows precipitation rate over Uttarakhand, nearby Kedarnath and Kedarnath for annual, seasonal and June month.

Fig. 4.1: Rain rate over Uttarakhand, nearby Kedarnath and over Kedarnath average for annual, monsoon and June month.

4.3.2. Precipitation analysis

Fig. 4.1.1 shows the results of 3 days accumulated rain (from 16-18 June 2013) over the simulation domain from TRMM and different versions of the WRF model. TRMM accumulated rain (Fig. 4.1.1a) shows heavy precipitation (greater than 100mm) over the western coast, northern India, Western Nepal and along with the area near to south eastern Bay of Bengal (BoB). Fig. 1b shows accumulated precipitation from the WRF WC25 simulation. The model reproduces major precipitation when compared to TRMM precipitation results, with some minor differences. Fig. 4.1.1c shows accumulated rain from

WRF25 simulation which again is like TRMM observation with minor differences. Fig. 4.1.1d shows the difference in accumulated rain produced by WC25 to WRF25 simulation. The results show that precipitation is reduced in central and north-eastern part of India with chemistry option turned on. However, northern India (majorly Uttarakhand), over Arabian Sea and Bay of Bengal shows increased rain in simulation with chemistry on.

Fig. 4.1.1: Three days accumulated rain from a) TRMM, and simulation of WRF at 25 km resolution b) WC25, c) WRF25 and d) difference of rain produced by aerosols in simulation.

Similar results are seen for the 4km resolution model simulations (Fig. 4.1.2). WRF with MOZCART chemistry (WC4) and WRF without chemistry (WRF4) show similar features of accumulated rain when compared to each other while there are differences when compared to the results obtained from TRMM. It must be noted that grid resolution between the model simulation and TRMM observation also leads to some of the observed differences.

Most of the focused area of study shows decrease in precipitation from the simulations with chemistry turned on whereas few areas also show increase in precipitation. Both sets of simulations (25 km and 4 km) show effect of aerosols on precipitation amount in either direction (i.e., increase or decrease). WC25 shows most of the area over and near to Uttarakhand produces more rain in presence of aerosols while WC4 shows less rain in presence of aerosols except few concentrated places.

Fig. 4.1.2: Three days accumulated rain from a) TRMM, and simulation of WRF at 4 km resolution b) WC4, c) WRF4 d) difference of rain produced by aerosols in simulation.

Study by Chawla et al., (2018) using combination of different parameterization schemes in WRF simulations shows that most of the combinations were able to capture spatial precipitation feature for 15th – 18th June 2013 [207], as in TRMM with some differences. Previous study using WRF-Chem simulation by Kedia et al., (2018) suggests 20% increase in precipitation over Uttarakhand due to chemistry, using 15 days average simulated and observed rain over the region for analysis [210]. Average precipitation and other parameters for 15 days shows aggregated impact of aerosols that is quite vague. Vertical profile and spatial and temporal distribution of aerosols were limited for specific event.

Fig. 4.2 presents time series of precipitation at four stations in Himalayan Mountains of Uttarakhand from 15th - 20th June 2013, these four-station present nearest stations to Kedarnath. In-situ observation at all four stations show that precipitation starts from morning of 16th and ends on the morning of 18th. Similar trend is observed through satellite for same time period. All four model simulations can correctly predict the start and end pattern of precipitation, and peaks in precipitation with some minor temporal shifts. At all the four stations, WC25 shows early rain whereas WRF25 shows delayed rain when compared to each other. Both WC4 and WRF4 shows delayed rain matching each other as well as matching with WRF25 simulation trend, but predict higher rainfall compared to WRF25 for the peak rain during these days. WC25 however matches the timing of the rainfall better with TRMM observations compared to other simulations.

Fig. 4.2: Precipitation from different simulation and observation from 15th - 20th June 2013 for a) Champawat, b)Pipalkoti, c)Pandukeshwar and d) Lambgarh .

Observation based report from IMD presents heavy precipitation on 16th and 17th June 2013, [208] which is evident in all model simulations and satellite observations too (Fig. 4.2). Other observation studies also show heavy precipitation on 16th and 17th over most of Uttarakhand region [204,206,209,213]. Most of the stations in Uttarakhand observed heavy precipitation starting from late evening of 15th, which increased on 16th and got further escalated on 17th, while rain stopped on early morning of 18th (Fig. 4.2) [209].

Table 4.2 shows coefficient of determination (R^2) between TRMM, in-situ observation and all four simulations with observations for the period from 15th – 20th June 2013. Over Kedarnath TRMM and model simulations show low value of R^2 (0.36-0.41). At other places, TRMM and in-situ data shows R^2 in the range of 0.32-0.60; R^2 for TRMM and model ranges between 0.32-0.95 except for Dehradun and R^2 between in-situ observation and model ranges between 0.23-0.93, except for Jolly Grant. R^2 at Jolly Grant between TRMM and in-situ observation is 0.60, between observation and model is less than 0.31. Observed accumulated rain at Jolly Grant was high as 200 mm/day (in-situ), model produces less than 100 mm/day during event days, and model does not perform well at Dehradun station too. Over other stations model replicates the strength and period of precipitation.

Table 4.2: R^2 of precipitation from different simulation with observed precipitation from in situ and satellite observation.

Simulation	TRMM	1		2		3		4	
Stations	Obs.	Obs.	Sat.	Obs.	Sat.	Obs.	Sat.	Obs.	Sat.
Kedarnath	NA	NA	0.36	NA	0.36	NA	0.40	NA	0.41
Champawat	0.52	0.40	0.95	0.63	0.70	0.60	0.74	0.60	0.74
Nainital	0.56	0.53	0.41	0.93	0.45	0.78	0.62	0.76	0.60

Jolly grant	0.60	0.31	0.32	0.02	0.01	0.28	0.06	0.21	0.04
Dehradun	0.32	0.28	0.27	0.14	0.02	0.41	0.06	0.36	0.03
Lambagrh	0.58	0.63	0.74	0.66	0.56	0.65	0.54	0.39	0.54
Pandukeshwar	0.49	0.23	0.74	0.41	0.56	0.36	0.56	0.36	0.56
Pipalkoti	0.40	0.23	0.57	0.67	0.45	0.42	0.44	0.40	0.43

Fig. 4.1 and 4.2 suggest that all model simulations adequately capture the spatial and temporal coverage of precipitation, with some difference in amount of precipitation. WC25 and WRF25 show up to 50 mm/day rain difference at some of the stations, whereas WC4 and WRF4 show negligible precipitation difference. Additional analysis suggests more rain at 25 km simulation without chemistry at Dhanauri (~20 mm/day), Jolly Grant (~60 mm/day), Dehradun (~70 mm/day) and Mandal (~100 mm/day). Whereas more rain is produced at 25 km simulation with chemistry in places like Kedarnath (~40 mm/day), Champawat (~60mm/day), Nainital (~15 mm/day), Lambagrh (~40 mm/day), Pandukeshwar (~10 mm/day) and Pipalkoti (~20 mm/day). WRF and WRF-Chem were able to simulate precipitation well over most of the observation stations, which is further corroborated by TRMM observations. Given the model's ability to replicate the rainfall over Uttarakhand, we present the model-based analysis on monsoon dynamics, cloud properties and aerosols during this event.

3.3. Monsoon Dynamics

Indian Meteorological Department (IMD), India and Department of Hydrology and Meteorology (DHM), Nepal reported onset of the summer monsoon on 15th and 14th June

2013, respectively. Due to heat low (high temperature leads to low pressure zone) over northern India and high-pressure zone over adjacent ocean, moisture moves with wind from ocean to northern India during monsoon. Fig. 4.3a shows counter-clockwise cyclonic motion of wind direction implies strong low pressure (WC25 due to full chemistry option) zone over northern India on 16th June, which guided the moisture from ocean towards the land. WC4 shows consistent winds flowing from south-east to north-west (Figure not shown). Fig. 4.3b shows strong low-pressure zone on 17th system, towards the north. Same low pressure zone further moved towards the western Nepal (Fig. 4.3d) on 18th which created flood situation in western Nepal (<https://www.icimod.org/?q=10932>); after 19th this system disappeared (Fig. 4.3e & f).

Fig. 4.3: Daily wind speed at 850 hPa from 15th - 20th June (a-f) Simulation-1.

Singh and Chand, (2015) had shown the presence of a low pressure zone over central India (Rajasthan and Madhya Pradesh) as simulated by their model on 16th June. Ray et al., (2014) reported presence of low-pressure system during 16th and 17th over central India [208]. Dynamical interaction of monsoon due to low pressure system over central India with mid latitude western disturbance results into heavy rainfall [2,204,208]. Similar wind pattern and low pressure were simulated in all the simulation. Precipitation pattern is also simulated well in the simulations with respect to observation and previous literature.

In-situ observation for all stations listed in supporting table shows strong low pressure near to surface, about 4-6 hPa lesser than average atmospheric pressure on 17th. WC4 and WRF4 simulations represent better pressure at different stations in comparison to simulation WC25 and WRF25 mainly due to higher model resolution which better reflects topography height. Low pressure indicates unstable atmosphere and higher probability of precipitation. High surface relative humidity ($\geq 90\%$) was observed during 16th and 17th and the model also simulated high relative humidity for all the stations ($\geq 80\%$). Persistent higher humidity indicates higher probability of precipitation in that area. Observation and model both show rapid decrease in relative humidity from the morning of 18th June. Observed surface temperature on 17th June at all stations fell ($\sim 3^{\circ}$ - 5° C) compared to average temperature. Similarly, WC25 and WRF25 shows temperature fall of $\sim 4^{\circ}$ - 6° C while WC4 and WRF4 shows a fall of $\sim 2^{\circ}$ - 6° C. All the parameters show normal atmospheric conditions from the morning of 18th June in comparison with event days. Literature based on observation shows 70-100% humidity, low pressure and low wind during event days over Kedarnath [21].

4.3.4. Cloud Property

Fig. 4.4 shows average cloud fraction (CF) from MODIS (Aqua and Terra) satellite (a-b) and average model simulated cloud fraction (c-d) for 16th and 17th June 2013. Both Satellite and Model shows similar feature on 16th (Fig. 4.4a, c), dense clouds from Arabian Sea to North India passing through central India along with dense clouds in south eastern Bay of Bengal. Both satellite and model-based observations show that all of Uttarakhand and western Nepal was covered by dense clouds on 16th. On 17th, satellite does not show dense cloud fraction over Uttarakhand and western Nepal whereas the model does simulate dense cloud fraction over area. However, on 17th, the satellite data does shows similar cloud

fraction features over Western Ghats, Arabian Sea and Bay of Bengal as seen on the 16th. Li et al., (2005) had discussed about derived cloud microphysical properties from MODIS [214].

Fig. 4.4: Average Cloud fraction hPa on 16th and 17th June a) and b) Satellite average from MODIS (Aqua and Terra), c) and d) Model respectively.

Model analysis reveals whole of Arabian Sea, Bay of Bengal and central India is covered with low and mid-level clouds (Figure not shown). In this study low cloud is consider up to 800 hPa, mid-cloud below 450 hPa and high cloud above 450 hPa. Along with low and mid-level clouds, Uttarakhand, Western Nepal, small part in Arabian Sea and Bay of Bengal was covered with dense high-level clouds on 16th and 17th June. Satellite observed low cloud top pressure (CTP) over Uttarakhand compared to surrounding areas (~300 hPa) on 16th and (~400 hPa) on 17th, indicating presence of high-level cloud over Uttarakhand.

Low cloud top temperature (CTT) was observed from satellite (~ -30°C to -40°C) on 16th and (~ -20°C to -30°C) on 17th over Uttarakhand and Western Nepal. CTT from model simulation was lower in comparison with surrounding over Uttarakhand and western Nepal

($\sim -10^{\circ}\text{C}$ to -20°C) on both days. WC4 simulates further cooler CTT on 17th ($\sim -30^{\circ}\text{C}$ to -40°C). Presence of aerosol mostly produces warmer cloud top at WC25 except some places near to Kedarnath, WC4 simulated changes in CTT variation ($\pm 15^{\circ}\text{C}$). Lower CTP and CTT indicates the deep cloud with high amount of precipitation [197].

At 25 km resolution, presence of aerosols affects cloud fraction by $\pm 25\%$ away from the major sources of emission (inferred from Fig. 4.1.1d). Presence of aerosols simulated more cloud at low level whereas decrease in the high-level clouds, while the mid-level clouds get affected in both ways over the domain of simulation. Similar results were simulated at 4 km resolution with and without aerosols for both days. The presence of aerosols played a role in creating warm clouds at central and eastern parts of India, the same region where aerosols affected precipitation negatively (Fig. 4.1.1d). Satellite data along with model shows low CTT and CTP over Kedarnath during 16th and 17th compare to previous days. Model indicates presence of dense high cloud over Kedarnath which could result in a heavy downpour.

4.3.5. Aerosol Concentration

Previous sections suggested presence of dense high-level clouds over Kedarnath (clouds above 6 km), so we analyzed aerosols above 6 km (above ~ 500 hPa). Our results show that over Kedarnath, there is an elevated concentration of anthropogenic and natural aerosols during the heaviest precipitation day. Fig. 4.5 shows area average concentration of black carbon (BC) over Uttarakhand ($\sim 29^{\circ}$ - 31°N , $\sim 78^{\circ}$ - 81°E) from 15th - 19th. Night of 17th shows highest BC concentration at 500 hPa ($> 0.25 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and above, columnar average BC concentration was higher by $\sim 0.1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ from previous day. Fig. 4.2 shows precipitation peak was present for similar period over most of the stations.

Further analysis of bulk aerosol species above 6 km (above ~ 500 hPa) over Kedarnath shows presence of elevated concentrations of anthropogenic and natural aerosols during

heavy precipitation days. Fig. 4.5 shows area average concentration of black carbon (BC) over Uttarakhand ($\sim 29^{\circ}$ - 31° N, $\sim 78^{\circ}$ - 81° E) from 15th - 19th. At 500 hPa BC concentration was elevated by $> 0.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$; at 300 hPa and above elevated BC concentration simulated during 16th and 17th. Night of 17th shows highest BC concentration at 500 hPa ($> 0.25 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and above, columnar average BC concentration was higher by $\sim 0.1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ from previous day. Fig. 4.2 shows precipitation peak was present for similar period over most of the stations.

Fig. 4.5: BC concentration from 15th - 19th June 2013 at 500 hPa, 300 hPa and columnar average.

Other bulk aerosol species like organic carbon (OC), dust (different size), sea salt (different size) and sulfate shows similar elevated peaks at 500 hPa and above. Table 3 presents difference in concentration of various aerosol species at 850 hPa, 500 hPa, 3 hPa and total column average. The methodology of calculating the difference in concentration is as follows:

For any aerosol species X (BC, OC, dust (all size), sea Salt (all size), sulfate),

$$\Delta X = \text{Area Average concentration (average (Non Precipitation dates))} - \text{Area Average concentration (average (Precipitation date))} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$X = \text{Column, 850 hPa, 500 hPa or 300 hPa}$

Non Precipitating dates = 15th , 18th, 19th and 20th

Precipitation date = 16th or 17th

Area Average over Uttarakhand (~29° – 31°N, ~78° – 81°E)

Most of the bulk aerosol species BC, OC, dust and sea salt shows elevated concentration at 850 hPa and above specially at higher elevation of 500 hPa. DUST5 decreases while Sea Salt4 and Sea Salt1 increase insignificantly on 16th and 17th at all elevations. Near surface (850 hPa) concentration of DUST4, BC and OC decreases during heavy precipitation events. At 500 hPa and above, BC, OC, Dust2, 3, 4 and Sea Salt2, 3 increases significantly during the event days. Sulfate concentration was less in column and near surface, whereas at 500 hPa and above concentration was significantly high. Formation of rain drop is more dependent on size of CCN particle in comparison with chemical composition of particle[215].

Table 4.3: Δ concentration X (different aerosols) in column and at 850 hPa, 500 hPa, 300 hPa for 16th and 17th June 2013 over Kedarnath.

Aerosols	16 th June 2019($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)				17 th June 2019($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)			
	Δ Column	Δ 850 hPa	Δ 500 hPa	Δ 300 hPa	Δ Column	Δ 850 hPa	Δ 500 hPa	Δ 300 hPa
BC	-0.001	-0.225	0.156	0.029	0.03	-0.039	0.154	0.031
OC	-0.023	-1.672	1.038	0.177	0.189	-0.473	0.981	0.152
DUST1	0.685	2.409	1.124	0.352	0.298	1.412	0.489	0.108
DUST2	1.264	4.893	2.069	0.775	0.615	3.033	1.212	0.227
DUST3	0.766	3.189	1.384	0.549	0.423	2.063	0.999	0.148
DUST4	-0.054	-0.764	0.357	0.149	-0.043	-0.773	0.387	0.042
DUST5	-0.031	-0.165	-0.027	0.003	-0.025	-0.137	-0.012	0.001
Sea Salt1	0.008	0.026	0.015	0.002	0.008	0.031	0.011	0.001
Sea Salt2	0.075	0.220	0.146	0.021	0.077	0.284	0.107	0.009
Sea Salt3	0.058	0.194	0.083	0.011	0.036	0.137	0.047	0.004
Sea Salt4	0.0002	0.0011	0.0001	0.00001	0.0001	0.0002	0.00003	0.000002
sulf	-0.028	-1.349	0.711	0.126	-0.056	-1.087	0.405	0.073

Aerosols act as IN and CCN, responsible for creating clouds and precipitation [195,196]. Model analysis of average columnar rain number concentration (RNC) and ice number concentration (ICC) over Kedarnath (Fig. 4.7 a-b), reveal elevated concentration of RNC and ICC during 16th and 17th June. Model simulation at 4 km with and without aerosols

shows small differences for rain and ice number concentration, similar results were repeated at 25 km resolution. On 17th, model simulations at 4 km shows much higher ICC compare to 25km resolution simulations, whereas RNC was much higher in 25 km resolution simulations in comparison with 4km resolution simulation on 17th. This justifies more rain over Uttarakhand in presence of aerosol at 25 km resolution compared to cloud resolving scale. On 16th, all models simulated good number of RNC whereas ICC was not significantly high over Kedarnath. Higher RNC delays the precipitation time, which leads to higher and deeper clouds [200] as observed by satellite and model over Kedarnath (Fig. 4.4a-b).

Fig. 4.6: Average columnar Rain (a) and Ice (b) number concentration from 15th - 19th June 2013.

On 17th June, above 500 hPa, significantly high amount of ICC was present, which justifies cooler cloud top, as observed by satellites over Kedarnath. RNC, ICC (Fig. 4.6) and precipitation (Fig. 4.2) patterns suggest two peaks. First peak before 17th, which was continuously increasing from the evening of 15th to 16th that resulted into downpour at late night of 16th – 17th. Second peak of RNC and ICC was present during daytime of 17th, which leads to precipitation on late evening but with less quantity. Probably high amount of ICC holds the precipitation in cloud which moved with synoptic circulation towards western Nepal on 18th, resulting into heavy downpour there.

Fig. 4.7 shows the difference in extinction coefficient profile along with difference in ICC and RNC on 16th and 17th June due to presence of aerosols. Both days show higher extinction coefficient between the heights 2 to 8 km, calculated from equation 1, whereas RNC significantly increases in presence of aerosols at 4-6 km on both days. ICC decreases significantly in presence of aerosols; all figures show decreased ICC above 6km during 16th and 17th. Satellites were not able to capture aerosol optical depth (AOD) during event day, even nearby AERONET station (over Kanpur) doesn't have data, and therefore AOD comparison with observation was not possible. On 17th CALIPSO shows 3% of data availability, data loss reported due to a ground station anomaly (https://www-calipso.larc.nasa.gov/products/lidar/browse_images/data_event_log.php?s=production&v=V3-30&browse_date=2013-06-17), whereas 16th and 18th passes were far from the area of interest.

Fig. 4.7: *Changes in Extinction coefficient, rain and ice number concentration profile over Kedarnath during (a-b) on 16th June and (c-b) on 17th June 2013 at 25 km and 4 km resolution respectively.*

Unusually, presence of anthropogenic and natural aerosols (BC, OC, Dust, sulfate and Sea Salt) in free troposphere above 2 km leads to increase in RNC which results in more precipitation over Kedarnath region. Result shows higher concentration of aerosols at elevated layers affected the ICC numbers negatively which resulted into more precipitation into region. Aerosols over the simulation domain affected the cloud and precipitation in either way.

We considered the parameters important to indicate severe weather such as Convective Available Potential Energy (CAPE), convective inhibition energy (CIN), vorticity and helicity [130]. CAPE was simulated high (≥ 1000 J/kg) over BoB, Arabian Sea and many parts of Indian subcontinent in WC25, whereas Kedarnath doesn't show high CAPE values during the event days. CIN was very less (≤ 50 J/kg) over most of the area except over Pakistan and Northern India (≥ 100 J/kg), during event days. Strong ($\geq 12 \cdot 10^{-5}/s$) vorticity is simulated in models along the low-pressure zone (Fig. 4.3). Strong helicity (≥ 400 m²/s²) also simulated over Arabian Sea and over Uttarakhand. Presence of aerosols affects the radiation over the region which results into changes on above parameters. At 25 km and 4 km, presence of aerosols shows ($\geq \pm 300$ J/kg) changes in CAPE, ($\geq \pm 50$ J/kg) CIN, ($\geq \pm 100$ m²/s²) helicity, and ($\geq \pm 6 \cdot 10^{-5}/s$) vorticity values over many part in the domain of simulation. Over Uttarakhand, presence of aerosols increased ~ 200 J/kg in CAPE, ~ 20 J/kg in CIN, up to 100 m²/s² in helicity and above $4 \cdot 10^{-5}/s$ in vorticity.

Fig. 4.8: Effect of aerosols on a) CAPE, b) CIN, c) helicity and d) vorticity at 4 km resolution (WC4-WRF4) during 17th June.

At 4 km simulation aerosols effect shows up to ± 200 J/kg changes in value of CAPE at the event day in the domain of simulation. (Fig. 4.8a), CIN values significantly affected by presence of aerosols. Whereas similar results are simulated at 25 km resolution simulation. Helicity and vorticity show strong variation in presence of aerosols over Kedarnath and nearby area at cloud resolving scale (Fig. 4.8c, d). Helicity and vorticity changes are not very evident at 25 km resolution. At cloud resolving scale variation in the parameters affected by orographic and thermodynamic are more evident than at low resolution simulations

Presence of aerosol doesn't only affect cloud and precipitation by acting as CCN and IN but also affects the dynamic weather index which indicates building up of severe weather. Results show presence of aerosols over plains and other parts over India reduced the cloud fraction and less IC formation leads to warm precipitation and less rain. Severe weather parameters CAPE, CIN, helicity and vorticity also show negative trend in presence of aerosols. Over the Uttarakhand and near to Himalayan foothills, CAPE, CIN, helicity and vorticity significantly increases in presence of aerosols. More aerosols led to more rainwater

and ice formation in clouds that led to higher cloud and resulted into downpour over Kedarnath and western Nepal.

4.4. Summary and Conclusion:

Long term (1998-2014) analysis of precipitation from TRMM over Kedarnath suggested that heavy precipitation during month of June over Kedarnath is unusual event. Analysis shows June of 2013 experienced highest precipitation compare to June month of any other year from 1998-2014, whereas 2013 year was recorded as normal monsoon year. We used six sets of model simulations at 25 km and 4 km resolution (three each), and further analysis was done using four sets of simulations (two from each resolution). We dropped two sets of simulations (one from each resolution), since chemistry without aerosols (MOZART) and without chemistry shows no significant difference in precipitation amount at both resolutions.

All model simulations captured TRMM observed spatial coverage of precipitation with some differences. Presence of aerosols shows significant increase in precipitation over Kedarnath and nearby area, whereas suppressed precipitation over central and eastern part of India was observed at 25 km resolution. Aerosols at cloud resolving scale (4 km resolution) shows similar results with more variation and differences in precipitation changes due to presence of aerosols. In situ observations and TRMM data over many stations near to Kedarnath shows that model can capture temporal trend and strength of precipitation with some differences. Model captured the consistent movement of low-pressure system from central India on 16th to Kedarnath on 17th and further towards western Nepal on 18th, as reported in literature, while it dissipated on 19th. Temperature, pressure and humidity are also well replicated by model with observation. Cloud properties such as cloud fraction, cloud top temperature and pressure is also well simulated by model as observed from satellite.

Model simulation shows deep clouds (above 500 hPa) over Kedarnath and some other parts over ocean on 16th and 17th. Model analysis suggested presence of aerosols above 500 hPa which may act as CCN/IC. High amount of RNC and ICC over Kedarnath on 16th and 17th explain the role of aerosols in heavy precipitation event over Kedarnath. Some the stations showed 100 mm/day increase in rain due to presence of aerosols, most of the stations showed $\sim\pm 40$ mm/day difference. Average profile analysis shows unusual presence of aerosols over Kedarnath and their significant effect on rain and ice concentration number, discussed as CCN and IN. The effect of aerosols on precipitation was not only limited to CCN and IN in clouds, its effect on radiation makes significant feedback on precipitation. Analysis of CAPE, CIN, vorticity and helicity show positive feedback of radiation in the region where precipitation was high and negative effect on the area where precipitation was less (Fig. 4.1.1d). Himalayan orographic lifting, fast moving monsoon due to low pressure generated from 15th – 18th June 2013, active westerlies and aerosols effect on cloud formation due to direct as CCN/IN and indirect radiative effect made this event so devastating. Further detailed analysis of such system is necessary to understand effect of aerosols and dynamics on cloud burst in Himalayan region and for predicting such system with good lead time.

Chapter 5: Outcomes and Future outlook

5.1 Summary

South Asian countries' and particularly India's economy is largely dependent on monsoon precipitation. Many studies in the past tried to understand monsoon circulation, aerosol-cloud interaction and transport of pollutants to the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere. Somehow, these studies did not focus on the crucial area to investigate during the monsoon season, i.e. mid-troposphere: at this layer most of the clouds form over South Asia. The presence of aerosols in the mid-troposphere can affect monsoon precipitation and result in drought and/or flood situations over the Indian subcontinent. We used the WRF-Chem model to understand the vertical transport of aerosols. Due to its unique property as discussed in chapter 1, and a reasonable lifetime, we selected black carbon for the research.

We started investigating the vertical transport of black carbon during the monsoon of 2013. To understand the convection activity over South Asia, we used long term TRMM lightning data over four locations - Mumbai, Kolkata, Lucknow, and Kathmandu. The result shows the period between May-June to be the highest lightning period over all the chosen cities. Typically, this period is considered as pre-monsoon over South Asia; Mumbai showed two peaks one was in pre-monsoon like other cities, and one at the reversal of monsoon. Parallely, we used monsoon onset and reversal data from the Indian Meteorological Department, India and Department of Hydrology and Meteorology, Nepal. Using information from TRMM lightning data, meteorological department data from Nepal and India, and literature, we classified seasons for this research as winter from December 2012 to February 2013, summer or pre-monsoon from 1st March to 9th June, monsoon from 10th June to 15th October and post-monsoon from 16th October to 30 November 2013. We used WRF-Chem to simulate November 2012 to November 2013, including one-month spine up time. Satellite

and AERONET observed aerosol optical data matches well with model simulated values. Observed black carbon concentration at many sites from South Asia agreed well with model simulation except central Himalayan cities like Kathmandu and Srinagar. Our analysis suggests Kathmandu and Srinagar simulation was majorly affected by two reasons. First one is improper emission inventory over the region that leads to lower concentration of black carbon and other species over central Himalaya throughout the year. Second reason is advection mechanism in model which needs an improvement for the Himalayan terrain as it leads to wrong concentration in different seasons, for instance pre-monsoon is higher than winter that is not observed experimentally.

As pre-monsoon and monsoon are the convective active periods in South Asia, we performed further analysis for this period only. Absorbing aerosol optical depth from OMI and MISR satellite shows higher values over the central part of India during monsoon compared to pre-monsoon. Model analysis shows similar results with black carbon concentration over the central part of India during monsoon. The model shows a consistent and significant amount of black carbon at 500 hPa and above. CALIPSO satellite observation shows the detection of smoke at the same level. This elevation is considered as mid-troposphere where most of the cloud forms and black carbon plays an important role in cloud chemistry. This feature is the first time reported in the scientific community using a regional model and validated with indirect satellite observations. Further analysis with high convection event-specific case study over four cities suggests black carbon is mostly uplifted above the planetary boundary layer during deep convection. After that, transport of black carbon is mostly driven by synoptic-scale circulation.

Once we knew black carbon is present at mid-troposphere over central India during monsoon, we tried to quantify the effect of black carbon along with organic carbon on incoming and outgoing radiation. For this study, we wanted to increase the carbonaceous

aerosol amount in the model to analyse radiation alteration. We chose real-time cases of high injection of carbonaceous aerosols in South Asia for the year 2013, which is an open biomass burning period. We analysed fire data from different fire inventories for more than 15 years. Data shows Myanmar and Punjab as the hotspot of open biomass burning over South Asia. Myanmar fire is mostly dominated by the forest fire in March and April whereas Punjab fire is dominated by crop residual burning during April-May and October-November. Punjab open biomass burning injects 2 to 3 times carbonaceous aerosol in the atmosphere compared to anthropogenic emissions during that period. Myanmar fire injects much more quantity in the atmosphere ~20 times than anthropogenic emission in that period. Carbonaceous aerosols from open biomass burning transports up to 3 km whereas the horizontal transport range is much higher. Vertical transport of fire emission is confirmed with the CALIPSO smoke product. Further analysis suggests a strong effect of carbonaceous aerosols on incoming and outgoing radiation flux. This effect reflects on primary weather parameters. Relative humidity near the surface increase with increasing concentration of carbonaceous aerosols whereas temperature, planetary boundary layer and wind speed decreases near the surface. Such changes reduce the dispersion of air pollutants and feedback to bad air quality. Delhi winter bad air quality during crop residue burning is one of the prime examples of the same (Fig. 5.1). Negligible effect on precipitation was simulated over both the regions, as the period of study was a dry period it was difficult to conclude anything with this effect. We further wanted to quantify the effect of aerosols on cloud and precipitation.

Fig. 5.1: a) Model simulated black carbon concentration from crop residue burning and b) satellite observed smoke on 29th October 2013.

We selected the Kedarnath flood which happened in the year 2013. Multiple WRF-Chem simulations were performed at 25 km and 4 km resolution to understand the effect of aerosols on precipitation at cloud-resolving and cloud parameterization scale. In this study, we discussed four simulations with and without aerosols at 25 km and 4 km respectively. TRMM based precipitation observation shows a similar special pattern as simulated by the model. In-situ and TRMM precipitation observation also shows good agreement with all model simulated amount of precipitation on a temporal scale. Wind pattern shows low-pressure creation over central India that leads to moisture from the Indian ocean to central India and moved towards Kedarnath and western Nepal on subsequent days. Cloud properties also agreed well with model simulation. Analysis of cloud top pressure and temperature suggest the presence of cloud at mid-troposphere. Aerosols analysis shows the removal of aerosols from the surface, whereas unusual concentration was simulated at the altitude where the cloud was present. With and without aerosol simulation suggest about a 20% increase in precipitation over Kedarnath. Cloud rain numbers and ice concentration were mostly affected by the presence of aerosols. Further analysis suggests that not only cloud properties alter with elevated aerosols at higher altitude but also thermodynamic parameters such as lifting index,

convective available potential energy changes, which enhances or suppresses bouncing of parcels.

5.2 Conclusion

Monsoon starts over South Asia typically from early June and retrieves by September. All over India and in other countries of South Asia surface observation during this period shows low quantity of pollutants compared to other seasons. A major part of pollutant washes off due to precipitation but a significant amount of pollutant transports above the planetary boundary layer. When pollutants are in free troposphere, their vertical and horizontal transports are driven by synoptic-scale circulation such as monsoon convection. Black carbon at 500 hPa and above is present over the central part of India during monsoon that is not evident in other seasons. Similarly, there is a possibility of the presence of other aerosols too. The results in chapter 3 suggest that black carbon strongly affects the incoming and outgoing radiation flux and these changes in radiation alters the temperature, humidity and other parameters. The presence of black carbon at 500 hPa and above can block a significant amount of radiation flux which alters moisture, temperature and other parameters in the atmosphere that are important in the formation and enhancement of clouds. Uplifted aerosols in mid-troposphere also affect the cloud chemistry, as discussed in chapter 4. Aerosols strongly affect cloud-water and cloud-ice contain within the cloud. The presence of a higher amount of black carbon increases cloud-ice contain that helps to deepen the cloud and delay the precipitation. It results in downburst in the latter part of the season.

This study suggests the presence of aerosols in the mid-troposphere. These aerosols have the potential to change cloud properties and atmospheric conditions too. In such cases, many places receive excess rain whereas other places get a minimum of rain. The effect of aerosols on cloud and precipitation is visible away from the major sources of emissions.

During monsoon, due to convection, aerosols from planetary boundary layer transport to free troposphere. Once it enters the free atmosphere then monsoon convection and winds decide its fate. Mostly they travel along with monsoon flow of moisture. Aerosols interaction with radiation and cloud creates uncertainty in monsoon extreme precipitation prediction. Further detailed study needs to be conducted to understand the nature of all the aerosols and their impact on radiation-cloud-precipitation to improve forecasting capabilities.

Fig. 5.2 summaries the importance of this thesis with respect to Kedarnath flood event (Chapter 4). Fig. 5.2a simply shows hot spot of BC over Indian sub-continent. Kedarnath area looks one of the cleanest areas compared to major hot spot region over Delhi. Fig. 5.2b shows BC concentration over 850 hPa, which is generally within the limits of PBL. At this elevation, BC is concentrated over most of the hot spots of BC emission presented in Fig. 5.2a. This indicates that during strong convection period, BC transports easily from source of emission to free troposphere as discussed in chapter 2. Fig. 5.2c shows BC concentration at 500 hPa, high BC concentration plumes are generally away from the hot spot region (Fig. 5.2a & b). At this elevation, towards the Kedarnath orographic lifting pushes air parcel and starts cloud formation. Synoptic winds were responsible to move BC towards Kedarnath with air parcel as mentioned in chapter 2. Over Indian subcontinent cloud forms at mid-troposphere (> 500 hPa). Presence of aerosols that act as ice nuclei in clouds at mid-troposphere reduces possibility of rain and helps cloud to grow deeper (chapter 4). Also, presence of absorbing aerosols at this level alters radiation and changes thermodynamic variables (chapter 3). At 300 hPa and above (Fig. 5.2d), BC presence at the level of deep cloud is detected over Kedarnath (Fig. 4.4). It indicates thunder clouds and strong downpour over the region as observed. Same system moved as it is towards western Nepal next day and caused floods in that area.

Fig. 5.2: Kedarnath flood analysis 17th June 2013; BC at different pressure levels a) near surface, b) at 850 hPa, c) 500 hPa and d) 300 hPa.

5.3 Suggestions and Future prospects

This thesis holds several limitations related to observations that need to address in future work for a better understanding of aerosol interaction with monsoon prediction, and better forecasting. This study explored aerosol (BC) vertical feature for one year (2013) and its impact on weather and cloud. Further, the study needs to explore the vertical feature of other aerosol species too and needs to identify features that are persistent in other years or not. A detailed study with all the aerosols that act as cloud condensation nuclei or ice nuclei needs to be understood in detail. Since observation of vertical profiling of aerosols is costly

and time-consuming, very less amount of data is available over the Indian subcontinent. The model persistently failed to capture the seasonality of aerosol concentration in the Himalayan region. That need to rectify in models using a good amount of observation of aerosol profiles in IGP and Himalayan region during pre-monsoon and monsoon.

Continuation of this study needs to focus on the quantification of radiation flux alteration by the presence of black carbon in the mid-troposphere. It needs to study in detail how the observed black carbon feature in mid-troposphere changes year by year, and varying ENSO conditions. Other aerosols' presence in the mid-troposphere needs to be quantified and studied in detail. Training models to capture such feature for better forecasting output is required. At last and most important, an economic study needs to explain the effect of such features in monetary terms. It will help to explain the consequences of aerosols emissions to policymakers for planning purposes.

Monsoon extreme precipitation cases can be improved if we consider the effect of aerosols on radiation and cloud with more certainty. The effect of aerosols on cloud and radiation is visible specially on precipitation quantity and pattern during monsoon. In policies and administration, there is a need to cut off the emission of aerosols at least during the monsoon period. It will help to curve the adverse effects of aerosols on monsoon precipitation on either way. Understanding mountain atmospheric dynamic and aerosol effect together helps to understand and predict cases like Kedarnath flood well in advance.

List of Publications

1. “*Transport of black carbon from planetary boundary layer to free troposphere during the summer monsoon over South Asia*” **P. Singh**, P. Sarawade, B. Adhikary, Atmospheric Research (2019) (IF=4.11)
2. “*Carbonaceous aerosol from open burning and its impact on regional weather in South Asia*” **P. Singh**, P. Sarawade, B. Adhikary, Aerosol and Air Quality Research (2019) (IF=2.78)
3. “*Role of aerosol in Monsoon extreme precipitation event over Himalayan region using WRF-Chem model at cloud resolving scale*” **P. Singh**, P. Sarawade, B. Adhikary, Advances in Atmospheric Sciences (2020) (In Communication)
4. “*Multi-Model Evaluation of Meteorological Drivers, Air Pollutants and Quantification of Emission Sources over the Upper Brahmaputra Basin*” A. Saikia, B. Pathak, **P. Singh**, P. K. Bhuyan and B. Adhikary, Atmosphere (2019) (IF= 2.04)
5. “*Short term disparity in chemical constituents and morphology of aerosol during festival event at urban region: A case study*” A. S. Pipal, K. Koser, **P. Singh**, P.G. Satsangi and A. Taneja, under review Heliyon (2019) (In Communication)

List of Presentations and Invited Talks

1. Poster presentation at Chemistry Climate Model Initiative (CCMI), 2019 training school and workshop, Hong Kong (4th – 9th August 2019).
2. Brownbag talk on “Role of black carbon in monsoon, weather and regional pollution” at ICIMOD, Nepal (30th July 2019).

3. Poster presentation at Atmospheric Composition and Asian Monsoon (ACAM), 2019 Training School and Workshop, Malaysia (24th – 28th June 2019).
4. Invited talk on “Air Pollution: Impact and Mitigation” at Kathmandu University, Nepal (5th June 2019).
5. Invited talk on “Basics of Air Quality Modeling” for master’s students at Tribhuvan University, Kathmandu Nepal (6th March 2019).
6. Poster presentation at Technical Workshop on High Impact weather, ICIMOD, Kathmandu (30th April – 1st May 2018).
7. Poster presentation at International workshop on Applications of Atmospheric Modeling; Air Pollution Impact Research in South Asia, ICIMOD, Kathmandu (17-19 April 2018).
8. Talk at Workshop on Atmospheric Pollution Instrumentation “Basics of Atmospheric Pollution Modeling”, ICIMOD, Kathmandu (15th March 2018).
9. Poster presentation at Air pollution, Climate and Health in Southern Asia and the HKH: Workshop & Science-Policy Dialogue, ICIMOD, Kathmandu (27th – 30th November 2017).
10. Oral Presentation and participation at 1st International training school on convective volcanic cloud and convection monitoring, detection and modeling at Castiglione del lago, Italy (4th – 9th October 2015).
11. Oral presentation at Indo-US Environmental Statistics Workshop-2015 at ISI, Kolkata. (2nd – 4th March 2015).

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